

The National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland for Pregnant and Postpartum Women

**Final Research Report
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Every contribution has helped ensure that these guidelines are evidence-informed and responsive to the needs of pregnant and postpartum women across Ireland.

Executive Summary

Purpose

To extend the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland ('Every Move Counts'), the Health Service Executive (HSE) commissioned South East Technological University (SETU) to develop Ireland's first population-specific physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines to include specific guidance for pregnant and postpartum women. This project sought to fill critical gaps, deliver evidence-informed guidance, and produce practical messaging for pregnant and postpartum women, health and social care professionals, sport and physical activity professionals, and policy and decision makers.

Development Process

A five-stage, mixed-methods process was employed from August 2024 to April 2025:

1. Evidence Summary

- Comprehensive reviews, international guidelines, key position papers, and recent systematic reviews, from the period 2019-2024, post the World Health Organisations (WHO) 2020 guidelines informed draft recommendations.
- Pregnancy and postpartum specific topics included intensity, frequency, types of activity (e.g., aerobic, strength, pelvic floor, balance), sedentary behaviour, contraindications, warning signs, and special populations (e.g., highly active women).

2. Project Team Review and Drafting

- The working group
 - provided iterative feedback on evidence summaries and initial drafts of guidelines and messages.
 - identified additional literature, contextualised findings for Ireland, and shaped tone, structure, and content.

3. Stakeholder Consultation

- Two anonymous online surveys engaged pregnant and postpartum women and professionals.
- Pregnant and postpartum women rated draft messages for practicality, clarity, and informativeness; professionals assessed clarity, appropriateness, and messaging relevance.

- Qualitative feedback highlighted areas for refinement in relation to areas such as clarity, tone and inclusivity.
4. National Stakeholder Meeting
- Based on feedback from public and professional engagement, key stakeholders (academics, healthcare professionals, decision makers, and advocacy groups) convened to refine the guidelines.
 - Focus areas included enhancing specificity within public health scope, balancing activity promotion with need for/importance of rest, addressing needs of special populations, and clarifying the role of healthcare professionals.
5. Consolidation and Finalisation
- Feedback from all stages was synthesised into final guideline documents, good practice statements, and tailored messaging suites.
 - Final revisions emphasised feedback for stakeholder consultation while respecting the limits of public health guidelines.
 - The final draft was sent to the Healthy Eating Active Living (HSE) team and further to the National Women and Infants Programme (HSE) for review ahead of publication.

Key strengths include clear, actionable recommendations that acknowledge differences in health status, baseline physical activity level, and context; balanced messaging that promotes both activity and rest; and explicit attention to safe practice across pregnancy stages and postpartum recovery. Although specificity around timelines and exercise modalities are moderated to maintain a public health scope, the guidelines aim to achieve balance between supportive messages and clarity for pregnant and postpartum women as well as health, social care, physical activity and sport professionals. It is noteworthy that separate guidelines and messages have been developed for pregnant and postpartum women, respecting the distinct physiological stages and lived experiences of women before and after birth. The addition of messages for policy and decision makers also aims to advocate for the resources and capacity building required to support and empower pregnant and postpartum women to be physically active.

Conclusions

The project provides Ireland with bespoke physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for pregnant and postpartum women, marking a significant advance in equitable, life-course public health policy.

Key recommendations reflected in the messages for professionals and policy and decision makers include:

Practice: Disseminate user-friendly materials (digital and hardcopy) to key stakeholders featuring key messages, examples, risk-warning checklists, and inclusive imagery.

To ensure pregnant and postpartum women are supported with physical activity, health and social care and exercise professionals should be trained in the area of physical activity, incorporating the evidence-base on safe exercise prescription, modifications and contraindications for this population.

In healthcare, there should be routine assessment of physical activity in pregnant and postpartum women. For insufficiently active women, brief advice and/or brief intervention should be provided. Where required, mechanisms should be implemented for signposting or referral to appropriately trained practitioners and/or physical activity opportunities.

Policy: Integrate guidelines into national maternal health strategies, routine surveillance, and funding for community-based prenatal/postpartum activity programmes.

Policy makers should aim to improve access to safe, affordable and inclusive opportunities for pregnant and postpartum women to engage in physical activity.

Policy makers should invest in public awareness campaigns to dispel myths and normalise safe physical activity during pregnancy and postpartum.

Research & Evaluation: Monitor guideline uptake, refine recommendations based on emerging evidence and evaluate impact on maternal and child health outcomes.

Introduction

The 'Get Ireland Active' National Physical Activity Guidelines for Ireland were published in 2009. These guidelines provided the foundation to promote physical activity in Ireland, however it did not include guidelines for sedentary behaviour nor guidelines tailored for people living with chronic disease or pregnant and postpartum women. In 2020, the World Health Organisation (WHO) published updated physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines (1). As a result, the Health Service Executive (HSE) commissioned an update of the Irish guidelines, which were published in 2024 *Every Move Counts* National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland (2). Every Move Counts also included messages for public and professional audiences designed to support the translation of the guidelines into practice. The updated 2024 guidelines did not include specific national level physical activity guidelines for pregnancy and postpartum. An extension to the guidelines, to include physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for this population was subsequently commissioned and is detailed in this report.

Physical activity conveys significant health benefits (3) both generally and relevant to these specific populations (4). In pregnancy and postpartum, physical activity can prevent pregnancy-related complications such as excessive gestational weight gain, gestational diabetes, hypertensive disorders, urinary incontinence, postnatal recovery time and prenatal and postnatal depression (5, 6). Additionally, physical activity for these populations is generally safe, (6, 7) and outweighs the health risks of sedentary behaviour, which research has identified in recent decades (8).

Despite this, physical activity levels during pregnancy and postpartum tend to be significantly lower than pre-pregnancy (9, 10). Fear of exercise-related risks is a barrier to physical activity participation, where concern that physical activity may aggravate symptoms or induce complications have been reported by pregnant and postpartum women, respectively (11, 12). Healthcare professionals have also cited a lack of knowledge and confidence in promoting physical activity to these populations (13, 14) National physical activity guidelines serve as recommendations, providing consensus on the scientific evidence, to raise awareness and enhance knowledge of the health benefits of physical activity among different groups. By establishing consensus-based, evidence-informed guidelines tailored to these populations and by translating them into actionable messages for women, healthcare professionals, and policymakers, guidelines can assist in removing barriers, dispelling myths, and empowering all stakeholders.

This report details the methodology of extending the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines "Every Move Counts" to include guidance for pregnant and postpartum women.

Development Process

Overview

The development of the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for pregnant and postpartum women in Ireland consisted of multiple stages spanning August 2024 to April 2025. A multi-phased and mixed methods approach was employed to allow for the iterative development of the guidelines and messages. It included 5 stages: 1) Evidence summary, 2) Project team review and drafting, 3) Online stakeholder consultation, 4) National stakeholder meeting, 5) Consolidation of feedback and final consensus.

This report and its subsequent sections, outlines the process applied to develop the physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for pregnant and postpartum women. Each stage combines a description of the methodology used and the corresponding outputs, where applicable.

Stage 1: Evidence Summary for Pregnancy and Postpartum Guidelines

Phase 1 involved desk-top reviews of the existing evidence and international physical activity guidelines in pregnancy and postpartum. The objectives of the evidence summary was to inform the development of draft guidelines and messaging for consultation prior to stakeholder consensus. Preparatory work included defining elements of the project scope (e.g., duration of post-partum period) and developing the search strategy and data extraction template. The focus of the review was:

- a. Existing international physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for pregnant and postpartum women.
- b. Evidence summaries and position papers published since the most recent WHO physical activity guidelines (1).

The process of collating the evidence summary included:

- a) A comparative analysis that was conducted across existing international physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines, which addressed pregnant and postpartum populations. This included the WHO Guidelines on Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour (1) and the national physical activity guidelines for the following native English-speaking countries; UK (15), US (16), Australia (17), Canada (18) and New Zealand (19). The analysis involved a comparison of consistencies and discrepancies, including nuances across guidelines with an emphasis on those published post the WHO guidelines, which were used as a referent.

- b) Position papers on physical activity and sedentary behaviour in pregnant and postpartum populations post 2019 were also compared for similarities, discrepancies and nuance (6, 20-22) and key recommendations were included in the analysis.
- c) Consultation with project team members who are experts in the fields of physical activity, exercise and sedentary behaviour in pregnancy and postpartum women also identified relevant evidence for inclusion.
- d) In addition, a purposive literature search, including grey literature was also performed to identify any landmark evidence since completion of the evidence summary by the WHO (1) in relation to public health focused, and population-based physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for pregnant and postpartum women. This search yielded two relevant, recent reviews (23, 24), which have informed this evidence summary:
 1. Hayman M, Brown WJ, Brinson A, Budzynski-Seymour E, Bruce T, Evenson KR. Public health guidelines for physical activity during pregnancy from around the world: a scoping review. *Br J Sports Med.* 2023 Jul;57(14):940-947. doi: 10.1136/bjsports-2022-105777. Epub 2023 Jan 5. PMID: 36604155
 2. Evenson KR, Brown WJ, Brinson AK, Budzynski-Seymour E, Hayman M. A review of public health guidelines for postpartum physical activity and sedentary behavior from around the world. *J Sport Health Sci.* 2024 Jul;13(4):472-483. doi: 10.1016/j.jshs.2023.12.004. Epub 2023 Dec 28. PMID: 38158180; PMCID: PMC11184298.

Evidence Summary Findings

Findings were summarised for both Pregnancy and Postpartum populations based on categorisation identified during the analysis, with reference to the WHO guidelines (1) and a summary of the evidence pertaining to each. Consideration points for the development of the guidelines were marked in **bold text**.

Note: The evidence summary presented in this report reflects a specific stage within the guideline development process. It is intentionally maintained in its original form to preserve the context and provide transparency into the deliberative process, highlighting areas identified for potential action or further investigation during the development of the guidelines.

Pregnant Women

1. General Recommendation and Messaging

According to the WHO (1) the general recommendation is that all pregnant women without contraindication should undertake regular physical activity (PA; Strong recommendation with moderate certainty evidence). The WHO (1) position is that there is no reason to alter the amount or frequency of recommended moderate-intensity PA for pregnant women compared to the general population and pregnant women should try to meet these guidelines where possible, as able, without contraindication. This is largely consistent across all guidelines, and position stands. Some nuance exists in terms of wording for example 'moderate-intensity PA is safe for generally healthy women during pregnancy' (16) and 'being active during pregnancy is safe' (17). The ACOG (American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists) Committee Opinion (6) states that PA and exercise are associated with minimal risks and have been shown to benefit *most* women, although some modification to exercise routines may be necessary due to normal changes and fetal requirements. Evidence calls for the wording to be considered in the guidelines to be inclusive of all pregnant women, rather than give the impression that only women with normal pregnancies should engage in PA. Particular caution should be maintained with regard to women with high-risk pregnancy, where the choice of the type and intensity of exercise must be made under the supervision of specialists (9) e.g., sometimes women will require exercise in bed (25). **Wording may be a consideration for consultation.**

The WHO (1) messaging is inclusive stating that the guidelines are for all women, irrespective of age, cultural background, or socioeconomic status. **It does not make specific reference to different populations (e.g., women with a disability, overweight or obese, athletes), which may need consideration** (23) (See Special Populations). The reviewed guidelines largely consist of public health guidelines as opposed to clinical guidelines, and as such the majority are in keeping with the WHO (1), which focuses on PA as an inclusive term for all movement, including more planned and structured exercise. The tone of the WHO messaging is positive and largely reflects gain frame messaging emphasising the benefits of PA such as decreased risk of pre-eclampsia (1). The Canadian guidelines advocate that PA should be considered as a frontline therapy for reducing pregnancy risk (18), which may reflect a move towards firmer positioning where guidelines published pre-WHO (1) were more cautious (23). Another important consideration is that the guidelines pre-Canada, were expert-based and not evidence based.

2. Intensity, Frequency and Duration of Activity

Intensity

In line with the WHO (1), almost all evidence summarised includes an exercise prescription approach. It is recommended that guidelines include a prescription in relation to frequency, duration and intensity in light of the evidence and in keeping with public health guidelines (23).

In terms of the intensity, the WHO recommend moderate intensity PA (1). This is in line with the majority of guidelines reviewed where only Australia also recommends vigorous intensity (17). A review by Hayman et al. (23) of 30 global guidelines also found the majority of guidelines recommend moderate intensity PA, where only Australia, Brazil and Spain recommend vigorous intensity. Hayman et al. (23) posits that the evidence-base for vigorous intensity is growing, yet it may be not strong enough to proceed with a recommendation until a stronger evidence-base is presented to address physiological changes during pregnancy, risk of injury, energy demands, and effects on fetal development (6). **This may be another point for consideration.**

A nuance to this is that the WHO (1) do recommend that women who, before pregnancy, habitually engaged in vigorous-intensity aerobic activity, or who were physically active, can continue these activities during pregnancy. Evidence suggests that vigorous intensity into the third trimester appears safe (6). A recent review of the global guidelines noted that guidance on vigorous intensity PA is vital for athletes and other women who may wish to continue exercising at high intensity during pregnancy and that while modifications may be required to accommodate the physical changes that occur, these are explained in few guidelines (23). Moreover, there is a growing evidence-base which indicates that even recreational athletes may benefit from vigorous to high intensity exercise, where no adverse outcomes have been observed in maternal and fetal health (26-32). **The level of nuance may need to be considered here,** and evidence calls for tailored messaging for **inactive, active and highly active women- point for discussion.** In this regard, light-intensity PA may also warrant inclusion. It is generally safe for previously inactive women to start a graduated programme of PA during pregnancy (23). The WHO (1) do not tailor exercise prescriptions based on PA levels but do align with the public health messaging that some activity is better than none explicitly, and also implicitly through suggested types of PA such as household chores and gardening.

Frequency and Duration

The WHO recommendation for PA frequency and duration is to do at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic PA throughout the week (1), and all guidelines have some recommendations on frequency and duration, although varied. Of the five guidelines reviewed with English as a native language, the WHO message was consistent with the US (16) and UK guidelines (15). The Australian guidelines recommend activity on most if not all days of the week for 2 ½ to 5 hours each week (17). Canada recommend PA should be accumulated over a minimum of 3 days with daily activity encouraged (18) and New Zealand recommend at least 30 minutes on most days (19). In the global review of guidelines, n=16 provided a specific recommendation on frequency ranging from daily to 3 or more per week, whereas n=8 provided general guidance (23) such as that provided by the WHO (1). Only the Australian guidelines recommend a duration of 150-300 minutes/week (17). **Messaging on frequency and duration will need to reach consensus.** All of the guidelines reinforce the message that some activity is better than none. Besides New Zealand (19), none of the guidelines with English as a native language, nor the WHO guidelines (1) recommend session bouts for pregnant women. The New Zealand guidelines recommend 'breaking up activity into smaller, more frequent and manageable chunks, such as 10 minutes at a time' (19) and **may warrant consideration for inactive populations or those with contraindications. This may also reinforce the point that targeted messaging is required for inactive, active and active groups where it is important to encourage bouts of activity for sedentary women, yet less applicable in the case of highly active women.**

3. Types of Physical Activity

The WHO guidelines (1) position aerobic PA as the primary recommendation for PA recommending at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic PA. The secondary recommendation is to 'incorporate a variety of muscle-strengthening activities. Adding gentle stretching may also be beneficial' (1). The majority of guidelines also position aerobic PA as the primary recommendation. Muscle strengthening PA is also a recommendation but more generalised in comparison rather than prescriptive e.g., 'PA choices should include strength training' (15). Australia recommend frequency of at least two days per week for muscle strengthening PA (17). These findings are also similar to the global review where almost two-thirds of guidelines provide advice on muscle strengthening but lack detail on prescription (23). There is a general paucity of research in the area related to safe muscle-strengthening activities for pregnant women that may be indicative of why the prescription is vaguer (23). **A general recommendation for muscle-strengthening PA with a recommendation of frequency may be advisable for muscle-strengthening exercises, although 12/30 guidelines in the global review**

provide examples that warrants discussion. Consider also the intensity of muscle strengthening exercises. Research also calls for recommendations to include advice on pelvic floor muscle training (PFMT) specifically for the prevention of urinary incontinence and long-term health benefits (6, 20). The WHO guidelines include a daily recommendation for pelvic floor muscle strengthening within ‘good practice statements’ (1). The Canadian guidelines (18) recommend instruction on the optimal technique to obtain optimal benefits. **Consider more nuanced guidance for PFMT.** In addition, postural, functional and balance exercises (e.g., Pilates, yoga and Tai-Chi) are also an important consideration and due to normal musculoskeletal complaints and increased risk of falls, **postural and balance exercise should be properly addressed in the guidelines (33-35).**

3a Recommended Activities

The WHO recommend that ‘for pregnant women, physical activity can be undertaken as part of recreation and leisure (play, games, sports or planned exercise), transportation (wheeling, walking and cycling), work, household chores, in the context of daily occupational, educational, home and community settings.’ (1). Country-specific guidelines vary in their recommendations of activities, yet evidence suggests that tailored and prescriptive advice is recommended (23). It should also be emphasised that **women may continue most forms of PA during pregnancy although some forms will require modification.** Types of PA are also dependent on experience and context. Position statements (6, 21) refer to the following exercises as ‘extensively studied and found safe and beneficial’: walking, swimming, stationary cycling, low-impact aerobics, modified yoga and Pilates, running/jogging, resistance exercises (using bands), stretching exercises and water-based exercises (e.g., hydrotherapy and water aerobics). **Some other examples of safe activity may warrant inclusion.** There should also be reference to other forms of activity (e.g., housework and gardening) to reinforce the public health message that some activity is better than none (2, 23), as aligned with the WHO (1). Warm up and cool down periods are also recommended (21).

3b Activities to Avoid

The WHO recommend that pregnant women should: ‘avoid participating in activities which involve physical contact; pose a high risk of falling; or might limit oxygenation (such as activities at high altitude, when not normally living at high altitude). Avoid activities in supine position after the first trimester of pregnancy and avoid PA during excessive heat, especially with high humidity’ (1). Position statements also recommend avoiding activities with changes in barometric pressure such as scuba diving where there is an inability of fetal pulmonary circulation to filter bubble formation (6). Others

provide more specific examples of activities to avoid e.g., surfing, horse-back riding (20, 21) or elaborate on risk factors such as ‘avoid contact sports or activities with increased risk of abdominal trauma’ (6). While there is **general consensus in the types of activities to avoid the wording and nuance to specific examples may be considered**. Examples may be also considered to reflect the culture and context (23).

There is varying level of agreement and evolving perspectives on PA in the supine position, where some recommend avoiding completely (23). The WHO recommend avoiding PA in the supine position after the first trimester (1). Other evidence suggests that supine position during exercise post 20 weeks may lead to decreased venous return (6). While maternal symptoms, such as dizziness and nausea, are typically the first indicators of reduced blood flow due to vena cava compression, the foetal response is also a critical factor. However, current evidence does not consistently show clinically significant adverse outcomes for the foetus due to short periods of supine exercise (36). A systematic review by Mottola et al. (36) concluded that there was insufficient evidence to ascertain whether maternal exercise in the supine position is safe or should be avoided during pregnancy. This finding has influenced a shift in some guidelines from blanket avoidance to recommending appropriate modifications based on individual comfort and symptoms (23). A recent global review highlighted a shift away from avoiding supine exercise towards appropriate modification of maternal PA in the supine position in more recent guidelines, recognising that while some high-risk groups (e.g., women with hypertension, fetal growth restriction, or multiple pregnancies) may receive individualised medical advice to avoid the supine position altogether (23). However, broadly restricting supine exercise for all women could unnecessarily limit safe movement options for the general pregnant population – **stance on supine position can be considered**. The Australian guidelines recommend more nuanced information; ‘After 28 weeks you should not do exercises lying flat on your back. Instead, tilt your upper body to a 45-degree angle or do the exercises lying on your side’ (17). Similarly, the Canadian guidelines offer ‘pregnant women who experience light-headedness, nausea or feel unwell when they exercise flat on their back should modify their exercise position to avoid the supine position’ (18). There is also some nuance in relation to high altitude training where recommendations state that women who are used to training at high altitude may continue to do so (23), the WHO refer to women living at high altitude.

3c Occupational Physical Activity

The WHO refers to occupational PA in the guidelines for pregnancy from the position that daily PA can be undertaken in that context (1). However, position stands call for additional research on

occupational PA during pregnancy (6). Studies published in the occupational PA literature suggest that repeated and prolonged heavy lifting may be associated with increased risk of miscarriage, preterm birth and other pregnancy-related adverse outcomes (23). Notably, position stands call for recognition that occupational health professionals may need to perform an analysis to determine maximum weight limits based on actual lifting condition within the workplace or help obtain accommodations (6). **This would align with the messaging that pregnant women should consult a health care professional (HCP) and may warrant inclusion.**

4. Types of Measurement of Intensity

The WHO do not appear to include recommendations for measuring the intensity of PA within pregnancy and postpartum guidelines (1). However, evidence supports a recommendation to assist with gauging level of intensity (6). Globally, 19/30 guidelines provide advice on how to assess intensity (23). There appears to be a move away from HR-based recommendations as seen in earlier guidelines and newer guidelines and position statements recommend measurements tools such as RPE (Borg scale) , the 'Talk Test' or descriptive guidance for measuring intensity e.g., moderate-intensity means moving at a pace leaving you slightly out of breath' (6, 17, 23). **Measurements of intensity including RPE, the 'Talk Test' and other descriptive messages may be important for exercise professionals and pregnant women, respectively.**

5. Sedentary Behaviour

The WHO (1) make a general recommendation for sedentary behaviour (SB) to limit time spent being sedentary. Also included are the risks associated with sedentary behaviour (all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease mortality, cancer mortality and incidence of cardiovascular disease, cancer and incidence of type-2 diabetes). The recommendation is to replace SB with PA of any intensity (including *light* intensity). Of the five guidelines with English as their native language only Australia (17) and New Zealand (19) make reference to SB with recommendations such as break up bouts of prolonged sitting. A recent global review found 14/30 guidelines provide advice on SB, which may be likely due to the lack of evidence on the impact of prolonged sitting in pregnant populations (23). In the WHO evidence summary, it is also stated that data on the general population was not extrapolated to inform the evidence base for SB in respect to pregnant women (1). Position stands do recommend that women who were sedentary prior to pregnancy can commence a gradual PA transition (6). In a similar vein, position stands highlight that activity restriction should also be addressed (6), which may be important in terms of messaging to challenge misconceptions about bed rest in pregnancy for both pregnant women and professionals. The WHO does not address activity restriction, but the ACOG position stand

(6) highlights there is no credible evidence to prescribe bed rest for prevention of pre-term labour or a reduction in preeclampsia risk and it should not be routinely recommended (increases risk of thromboembolism, bone demineralisation, deconditioning, including negative psychosocial effects). Indeed, based on the evidence available, research has suggested that recommending bed rest to treat pregnancy complications may be considered an unethical approach (37). **Discussion may be needed on the type and level of advice (general or instruction) for SB and whether to include messaging on activity restriction.**

6. Benefits of Physical Activity for Maternal and Fetal Health

The WHO states that in pregnant women, PA during pregnancy confers benefits on the following maternal and fetal health outcomes: decreased risk of pre-eclampsia, gestational hypertension, gestational diabetes, excessive gestational weight gain and delivery complications (1). An umbrella review on the benefits of PA during pregnancy suggested strong evidence that moderate-intensity physical activity reduced the risk of excessive gestational weight gain and gestational diabetes (38). There is a general consensus across guidelines that PA is safe during pregnancy and associated with a variety of health benefits for both maternal and fetal health (23). Others include reference to the benefits for psychological and mental wellbeing (21). There are some differences in terms of messaging approach where the focus may be on risk of inactivity e.g., inactivity is a risk factor for maternal obesity and pregnancy related complications including gestational diabetes and a lower incidence of vaginal delivery (6). **Discussion on the framing of the messaging and the benefits listed may be needed.**

7. Warning Signs to Cease Activity

The WHO makes a general recommendation that 'pregnant women should be informed by their health-care provider of the danger signs alerting them as to when to stop; or to limit physical activity and consult a qualified health-care provider immediately should they occur' (1). The Australian and Canadian guidelines also include specific warning signs to cease PA such as; persistent dizziness, excessive shortness of breath, chest pain, painful uterine contractions, vaginal bleeding, loss of fluid from the vagina or severe headache (17, 18, 23). The recent global review highlights that all women and their health professionals should be aware of the warning signs to cease activity (23). Evidence also supports that the provision of specific advice on safe and unsafe activities are more likely to increase PA and exercise behaviours (23). **Therefore, specific warning signs may warrant inclusion.**

8. Contraindications

The WHO guidelines make a general recommendation that PA is safe for pregnant women without contraindications and that all pregnant women should be under the care of a health-care provider for antenatal care who can advise on special considerations given their medical history and any contraindications to participating in PA during pregnancy (1). Other position stands state that most pregnant patients can exercise and there are few contraindications in which aerobic exercise is absolutely contraindicated, although a thorough clinical evaluation should be conducted before recommending an exercise programme to ensure non-medical reason to avoid exercises (6). Recent works involving the Get Active Questionnaire for Pregnancy (GAQ-P) presents the view that while historically, all pregnant women were advised to speak to their obstetric care provider about whether or not it was advisable to be physically active during pregnancy, this created a significant barrier to physical activity participation, and with high-quality evidence supporting the safety and health benefits for pregnant women it may no longer be warranted (39, 40) . However, identifying the small number of women who may develop a contraindication to exercise during pregnancy is essential. The GAQ-P was designed to be self-completed by pregnant women for this purpose, where based on their responses they will have a clear direction that they are at low risk for contraindication to prenatal physical activity and can begin or continue physical activity, or they will be directed to obtain additional screening with their obstetric care provider (39, 40). The WHO guidelines do not list specific contraindications to PA during pregnancy and of the five national guidelines reviewed the Australian guidelines (17) were the only one to list specific considerations (e.g., incompetent cervix, ruptured membranes, persistent bleeding in the second and third trimester, placenta previa). A systematic review that considered the evidence for absolute and relative contraindications found that the majority of contraindications were based on expert opinion and there was minimal empirical evidence to demonstrate harm of exercise and benefit of activity restriction (as mentioned under sedentary behaviour) (41). The review found that 11 complications (e.g., gestational hypertension, twin pregnancy) previously classed as contraindications, did not support activity restriction and women may benefit from regular PA with or without modifications (41). However, cardiorespiratory disease, placental abruption, vasa previa, uncontrolled type 1 diabetes, intrauterine growth restriction, active preterm labour, severe pre-eclampsia and cervical insufficiency are associated with strong potential for maternal/fetal harm and warrant classification as absolute contraindications (41). Similarly, to warning signs to cease PA, research highlights that pregnant woman should be informed of the contraindications and **discussion is warranted on whether to give specific examples as mentioned above and also to consider messaging to avoid misconceptions on other complications where it is safe to exercise.**

9. Other Considerations

The WHO guidelines (1) list other considerations including; avoiding activity during excessive heat especially with high humidity and staying hydrated by drinking water before, during, and after PA. There is a general consensus for inclusion of these considerations (23). The Australian and New Zealand guidelines also make recommendations in relation to clothing including wearing appropriate shoes, non-restrictive clothing and a supportive bra (17, 19). Other messaging within the Australian guidelines included; messaging in relation to weight gain during pregnancy e.g. ‘It is normal to gain some weight during pregnancy. However, gaining too much extra weight during pregnancy can affect your health and the health of your baby’, highlighting changes that occur with balance and centre of gravity and cautioning around stretching while there is extra ligament flexibility due to pregnancy hormones (17). **A discussion point will be which additional considerations to include.**

10. Special Populations

The WHO guidelines do not explicitly address special populations (1) although there is general messaging for athletes e.g. ‘When considering athletic competition or exercising significantly above the recommended guidelines pregnant women should seek supervision from a specialist health-care provider’. Similarly, position stands highlight that women considering athletic competition or PA significantly above recommended levels should contact their HCP about associated benefits and risks (21). Evidence from position stands also suggests vigorous intensity PA into the 3rd trimester appears safe for healthy pregnancies but further research is needed on the effects in first and second trimester and of exercise intensity exceeding 90% max HR (21). Few guidelines offer specific advice for highly active women, including athletes and safe upper limits for intensity/ duration (23). The general consensus on guidelines that include **highly active women/athletes** as a specialist population is that in a healthy pregnancy their activity can continue under supervision (1, 6, 20). Research has called for the inclusion of guidance on vigorous PA in national guidelines as vital for athletes and other women who may wish to continue exercising at high intensity during pregnancy and where modification to PA may be required to accommodate physical changes throughout the pregnancy (23). Both the Australian and Canadian guidelines are examples of more tailored recommendations: Australia: ‘Provided they have a pregnancy without contraindications (also known as ‘complications’), previously highly active women, including athletes who are already exceeding the amount of physical activity described in the Guidelines, may continue with their physical activity/exercise program, but should modify their activities as their pregnancy progresses, with advice from an informed health professional’ (17) and Canada; ‘Elite athletes who continue to train during pregnancy are advised to

seek supervision from an obstetric care provider with knowledge of the impact of vigorous-intensity physical activity on maternal, fetal and neonatal outcomes (18).’ **The level of messaging included for highly active women and athletes during pregnancy should be discussed.**

Similarly, a review of the public health guidelines for PA during pregnancy around the world, recommends that tailored advice is offered to **inactive, active and highly active women** (23). Two-thirds of global guidelines provide specific advice for these groups currently and the evidence supports that this type of more targeted messaging is more likely to increase PA (23). This is also supported by a recent scoping review on PA messaging (42). As above, the WHO guidelines recommend some activity is better than none as well as general recommendation of moderate-intensity aerobic PA, where vigorous PA can continue for those habitually active (1). Examples of other tailored messaging include ‘if pregnant and postpartum women are not meeting the recommendations, doing some physical activity will benefit their health start by doing small amounts of physical activity, and gradually increase frequency, intensity and duration over time’ (6). or ‘For pregnant women not currently meeting these Guidelines, a progressive adjustment toward them is recommended’ (18). Considering pregnancy symptoms, the Canadian guidelines also recommend: ‘There may be periods when following the guidelines are not possible due to fatigue and/or discomforts of pregnancy; women are encouraged to do what they can and to return to following the recommendations when they are able’ (18). **Tailoring messages to inactive, active and active women may lead to more inclusive messaging and engagement** (23, 42). **The message that supervised exercise is more effective (6) should also be considered where exercise physiologists and/or prenatal exercise specialists have the pedagogical skill to ensure proper technique and adaptation.**

Pregnant women living with **obesity** may also be a special population that warrant inclusion. Position stands highlight that woman with obesity should be encouraged to engage in modified PA and start with low-intensity short periods of exercise and gradually increase. This can lead to modest weight reductions with no evidence of adverse outcomes (6). The Canadian guidelines also offer specific recommendations for overweight or obese populations (18). **The inclusion of populations with obesity should be considered.**

Another population for consideration is pregnant women with a **disability**. While there is no explicit mention of these groups across the evidence reviewed, **it may warrant consideration from an inclusivity standpoint.**

11. Guidelines for Health Care Providers and Exercise Professionals

Some evidence presented below has been extracted from the ACOG committee opinion (6) that may be applicable in terms of messaging for health and social care providers and exercise professionals:

- Pregnancy is an ideal time for behaviour change and adoption of healthy lifestyle because of increased motivation and frequent access to medical supervision.
- A patient is more likely to increase PA if their HCP recommends that they do.
- Consider Motivational Counselling such as brief intervention (in women with uncomplicated pregnancies and no contraindications).
- Principles of exercise prescription do not differ from the general population.
- Most pregnant patients can exercise.
- It is important to identify women who may develop contraindications to PA during pregnancy. Consider the use of the 'Get Active Questionnaire for Pregnancy' (GAQ-P). The GAQ-P was designed to be self-completed by pregnant women for this purpose. Answering individual questions, they are able to easily self-assess their health, the course of pregnancy and the level and quality of physical activity undertaken so far, both during and before pregnancy. Based on their responses to these questions, they will have a clear direction that they are at low risk for contraindication to prenatal physical activity and can begin or continue physical activity, or they will be directed to obtain additional screening with their HCP.
- HCPs should evaluate women with medical or OB complications carefully before making recommendations on PA.
- Pregnancy results in anatomic and physiologic changes that should be considered when prescribing exercise (weight gain, shift in gravity that can lead to progressive lordosis, increase in the forces across joints and spine during weight bearing exercise).
- 60% of women experience low back pain. Strengthening abdominal and back muscles can minimise this risk.
- Activity restriction should not be avoided as a treatment to reduce preterm birth risk.
- Aerobic training in pregnancy can increase aerobic capacity in normal and overweight women.
- Decrease in subjective workload and max exercise performance equates to limited ability for strenuous PA (particularly if overweight or obese).
- There is an association with exposure to heat (saunas, hot tubs) and neural tube defects **but** exercise not expected to increase core body temperature to range of concern.
- Exercise programmes that lead to an eventual goal of 20-30 mins/day on most or all days of week should be developed and adjusted as medically indicated.

- RPE more effective means to monitor exercise than HR. Moderate intensity should be 13-14 (somewhat hard) on Borg scale. Or use the 'talk test'
- Additional research is needed to study the effects of exercise on pregnancy-specific conditions and outcomes and to clarify further effective behavioural counselling methods and optimal type, frequency and intensity of exercise.

Some messaging above may be considered for professionals.

Postpartum Women

The evidence summary for postpartum (PP) women will be outlined below. Some detail is consistent with guidelines for pregnancy and further detail will be included where nuances exist.

1. General Recommendation and Messaging

Guidelines for PP women are consistent with those for pregnant women where PP women without contraindication should undertake regular PA (1). The WHO recommends PP women 'return to physical activity gradually after delivery, and in consultation with a health-care provider, in the case of delivery by Caesarean section'. A recent review of public health guidelines for postpartum PA and SB highlights more variation in consensus across countries in comparison to a review of the guidelines for pregnant women (23, 24), where the guidance for PP is more cursory than the pregnancy guidelines related to PA. The Australian guidelines dedicate a separate page to address the PP period (20), and research has called for more nuanced guidance for PP women as opposed to general recommendations that are mixed with guidelines for pregnant women where warranted (24) (e.g., in the transition back to PA, for PFMT and SB during while breastfeeding). **Consider more tailored messaging for PP women. In addition, consider the tailoring of messaging where when some contraindications are present it is possible to engage in PA with modification.**

2. Exercise Prescription, Types and Transition Back to PA

As with pregnant women, the WHO guidelines recommend 150 minutes of moderate-intensity PA spread throughout the week with the incorporation of strength training exercises. A recent review of public health guidelines for PP PA and SB highlights a lack of guidelines for transitioning to PA for both active and inactive women (24). The duration of PA also ranged from 150-300 minutes per week (24). Australian guidelines specify to gradually increase PA until the PP check-up at six weeks (17), and the UK (15) recommend a gradual progression from light to moderate/vigorous intensity with emphasis on individual recovery e.g., 'the timing of resuming PA after childbirth is different for everyone' (17). Guidelines from the US state that there is no evidence of negative impact of PA during PP, so unless a woman has medical reasons to avoid PA during the PP period, she can begin or continue light- to moderate-intensity aerobic and muscle-strengthening PA (16). The New Zealand guidelines recommend that if PA is maintained throughout pregnancy, a PP woman should be able to return to light activity fairly quickly but that it is best to talk to a HCP and medical clearance will be needed in the case of a caesarean (19). A recent review of public health guidelines for PP PA and SB globally,

found overall, that most countries recommended frequency and/or duration as well as types (e.g., aerobics; pram walking, cycling, dancing and muscle strengthening; resistance exercises, PFMT and other behaviours such as active commuting, gardening, household chores). There were a mix of recommendations for intensity, n=17 recommend moderate and n=10 recommended vigorous. The research highlighted **the limited inclusion on 'light intensity'** where its omission particularly in replacement for SB may be a missed opportunity (24). Similarly, to the evidence on pregnancy (23), few guidelines tailored messaging to inactive, active and highly active groups which is recommended (24). **Consider also advice for special populations in line with pregnancy.** Another recommendation was that while PP guidelines addressed frequency, duration, type and intensity of PA, other important considerations were not addressed e.g., physical environment (where), social (with who) and instruction (supervised or not, individual or group based) (24). Many guidelines recommend strengthening exercises, but frequency, intensity and progression were also vague. The same applies to PFMT (where position stands recommend PFMT exercises should be resumed immediately (6, 21)) and other types of activities that include baby (stroller walking) that should be mentioned considering time spent with baby (24). Guidelines should make specific connections to the general population guidelines as the general aim should be the transition back to PA (24). **Messaging on transitioning back to PA as well as exercise prescription (including tailored messaging) for PP and whether to suggest types should be considered. More nuanced guidance on PFMT may also need to be included (33).**

3. Delivery Type and Defining the Postpartum Period

There are inconsistencies in defining the PP period (or lack of definition) across the current guidelines. The PP period should be explicitly defined when providing guidance on PA as it can last up to a year or longer if still breastfeeding (24). In addition, there was a general lack of advice found across guidelines tailored to phases of PP even though PA and SB can differ by phase e.g., mother-infant pairs spend more time breastfeeding in PP, which results in more SB (24). **Consider defining the PP period and tailoring messaging to phases of PP.**

Delivery type is also an important consideration as supported by position stands (6, 21). The WHO guideline advises a gradual return to PA in consultation with a HCP in the case of delivery by caesarean (1). Research suggests this is a simplistic dichotomy as vaginal delivery does not guarantee lack of complications (e.g., episiotomy/perineal laceration). In addition, where a vaginal delivery is absent of complications physiological complications also need consideration (abdominal separation, weakened PVM resulting in urinary/faecal incontinence (24)). While a review of evidence may be needed for

more specific exercise prescription, **consider emphasising the need for additional considerations beyond categorisation of delivery type.**

4. Sedentary Behaviour

The WHO evidence summary also stated that data on the general population was not extrapolated to inform the evidence based for SB in respect to PP women (1), where the recommendations are the same for pregnant populations. As previously outlined, the phases of PP may have important considerations for SB (24). A review of the guidelines outlined that 11/22 guidelines made some statement about SB that were general in nature e.g., 'Minimise the amount of time spent in prolonged sitting' (20, 24). Only one of the guidelines (Finland) reported benefits for reducing SB in PP, which includes improved blood circulation, reduced strain on the body and activation of muscles. Considering time spent with baby, advice may also consider incorporating active childcare to limit SB. **Statement on SB may apply to both pregnant and PP but consider more nuance for phases of PP.**

5. Benefits and Considerations

Alongside the benefits of PA for maternal and fetal health, the WHO outline the benefits for PA for PP as a decreased risk of PP depression and fewer newborn complications (1). The majority (n=10) of other guidelines cite benefits for weight management or reducing depression (n=9). Other benefits were cited but lacked consensus (24). An umbrella review on the benefits of PA during PP suggested strong evidence that moderate-intensity PA reduced the risk of postpartum depression (38). Insufficient evidence was available to determine the effect of PA on postpartum weight loss and postpartum anxiety (38). Conveying to PP women that they can continue to breastfeed while being physically active is an important topic for public health guidance and evidence suggests breastfeeding women are more likely to engage in PA if they receive information about the topic (24). Some guidelines state that there is no evidence that PA has an impact on breastmilk composition, quality or quantity (24). The evidence that PA does not impact the quantity or quality of breastmilk was graded 'very low' by Australia (17, 24). The ACOG committee opinion highlights that regular aerobic exercise in lactating women has been shown to increase CV fitness without affecting milk production, composition or infant growth (6). Advice for breastfeeding women was to consider expressing before exercising to avoid discomfort of engorged breasts and ensure adequate hydration (6). **Consider messaging in relation to breastfeeding an PA for PP women.**

6. Guidelines for Health Care Providers and Exercise Professionals

Some evidence presented below has been extracted from the ACOG and the American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) committee opinions (6, 21) that may be applicable in terms of messaging for health and social care providers and exercise professionals:

- Women's level of participation in PA diminishes after childbirth. The PP period is an opportune time for HCPs to recommend/reinforce PA.
- More frequent PP visits with HCP are recommend beyond usual 1-2 for tailored PA advice.
- Routine medical clearance before returning to PA PP is no longer recommended. However, identifying contraindications before beginning or returning to PA during the PP period remains important.
- Exercise routines may be resumed gradually after pregnancy as soon as medically safe, depending on mode of delivery (vaginal/caesarean) and medical or surgical complications and other individual factors.
- Some women are capable of resuming PA within days of delivery.
- Mild PA with pelvic floor exercises and stretching should be able to be resumed immediately.
- Abdominal strengthening exercises have been shown to decrease the incidence of diastasis recti abdominus and decrease the inter-rectus distance in women who gave birth vaginally or by caesarean.

Stage 2: Project Team Review and Drafting

A project team (listed on page 2) with relevant expertise was established to oversee the development of the pregnancy and postpartum guidelines, to ensure credibility, relevance and practicality. The team was engaged throughout the development process and played a key role in reviewing and interpreting the available evidence. Early in the process they were invited to recommend additional relevant literature and to help contextualise international findings within the Irish health system. Team members were also consulted during the development of the evidence summaries, providing iterative feedback, ensuring a collaborative effort on the development of evidence-informed guidelines and messaging. Following this, the completed evidence summaries were provided to the team, with an accompanying initial draft of the guidelines and messages. The team was given time to review and consider this information and subsequent meetings for each group were convened. The Chair facilitated discussion on both the evidence summary and draft guidelines and messages and feedback was noted. Following the meeting, the team was asked to provide further input remotely. The feedback was used to refine the initial drafts to produce drafts for wider stakeholder consultation. The project team's insights were instrumental in refining the guidelines ahead of wider stakeholder consultation. Their feedback helped shape the tone, structure, and content of the next drafts, ensuring that they were both scientifically robust and responsive to the needs and contexts of the target population. The output of the project team review was a draft of the pregnancy and postpartum guidelines. Specifically, the drafts included:

- i. An introduction outlining the scope of the guidelines and a brief evidence summary of the benefits of physical activity and risk of sedentary behaviour in the population
- ii. The physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines
- iii. Good practice statements
- iv. Specific population considerations
- v. Messages for users (pregnant and postpartum women)
- vi. Messages for health and social care professionals
- vii. Messages for physical activity professionals

Stage 3: Stakeholder Consultation

The draft guidelines and messages were disseminated for stakeholder consultation in the form of an anonymous online survey. Stakeholders included end users (pregnant and postpartum women), professionals and practitioners working with end-users (from both the health and physical activity sector) and others (i.e., academics, professionals within support structures advocacy and representative bodies, policymakers). End users were defined as women currently pregnant or postpartum, having given birth in the previous 12 months.

Stakeholders were recruited through the online dissemination of the study information and survey. The HSE acted as a dissemination partner and distributed the study information through email, website and social media channels. The information was disseminated through SETU online platforms and through the networks of the proj team. Other gatekeepers such as representative bodies, e.g., patient charities, support groups, were asked to share the information through their communication channels. This process received ethical approval from the School of Health Sciences Research Ethics Committee at South East Technological University Reference No: SETU/HSREC/24/25/004.

The survey was administered via the Qualtrics platform with tailored versions based on participant type. The survey for pregnant and postpartum women presented only the relevant draft messages. Through both open and closed questions, the surveys collected data on perceptions of the level of practicality, clarity and informativeness of the messages. The survey for professionals and practitioners working with these populations were presented with the relevant guidelines, good practice statements, specific population considerations and messages for professionals. This survey collected data through both open and closed questions on participants perceptions of acceptability. The domains of acceptability assessed included clarity and appropriateness. Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive statistics and qualitative data using thematic analysis.

Responses were analysed to determine levels of agreement with key elements of the guidelines and to identify recurring themes across stakeholder groups.

Stakeholder Consultation Findings

Demographic Characteristics of Pregnant and Postpartum Survey Respondents

Over four hundred (n=426) members of the target population (pregnant and postpartum women) responded to the survey, with a majority aged 30-39 years (79%). Of these, nearly half (47%) were currently pregnant and 43% were in the postpartum stages within the past year. Most respondents were from urban counties, with the highest response rate from Dublin (25%). The majority (75%) had

third level education, with a significant majority identifying as white (93%). Most respondents (92%) rated their health as good or very good, with the majority in employment (81%; See Table 1 for detailed demographics)

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of pregnant and postpartum survey respondents

Age Category	18-24 years: (n=5, 1.3%) 25-29 years: (n=36, 9.7%) 30-39 years: (n=293, 78.8%) 40-49 years: (n=36, 9.7%) 50-59 years: (n=2, 0.5%)
Geographical Location	Dublin: (n=93, 25%) Cork: (n=47, 12%) Galway: (n=21, 6%) Wexford: (n=23, 6%) Waterford (n=20, 5%) Kildare (n=20, 5%)
Ethnicity	White: (n=347, 93.8%) Black/Black Irish: (n=6, 1.6%) Asian/Asian Irish: (n=14, 3.8%) Other (Mixed): (n=3, 0.8%)
Education	Lower secondary: (n=1, 0.3%) Upper secondary: (n=16, 4.6%) Technical/Vocational: (n=8, 2.3%) Advanced Cert./Apprenticeship: (n=30, 8.7%) Bachelor's Degree (n=134, 38.8%) Postgraduate: (n=145, 42.0%) PhD or higher: (n=11, 3.2%)
Employment Status	Working for payment/profit: (n=303, 81.9%) Looking for first job: (n=1, 0.3%) Short-term unemployed: (n=3, 0.8%) Long-term unemployed: (n=15, 4.1%) Student: (n=3, 0.8%) Looking after home/family: (n=29, 7.8%) Unable to work due to sickness: (n=3, 0.8%) Other/Maternity leave: (n=13, 3.5%)
Health Status	Very good: (n=183, 49.3%) Good: (n=161, 43.4%) Fair: (n=22, 5.9%) Bad: (n=4, 1.1%) Very bad: (n=1, 0.3%)
Pregnancy/Postpartum Status	Currently pregnant: (n=175, 47.2%) Gave birth < 6 weeks: (n=29, 7.8%) Gave birth < 6 months: (n=60, 16.2%) Gave birth < 12 months: (n=72, 19.4%) Gave birth > 12 months: (n=21, 5.7%) Other (e.g., miscarriage): (n=14, 3.8%)

Table 2 details the levels of acceptability (practicality, clarity and informativeness) for each of the presented pregnancy messages rated by respondents. The following is a summary of the findings (See Appendix 1 for draft guidelines and messages presented at this stage and appendix 2 for link to final document):

Message 1: General Recommendation: The first message presented the general physical activity recommendation for pregnant women and most respondents (82.9%) agreed that the presented iteration of the message was practical, with 47.0% strongly agreeing. For clarity, the majority reported the message as clear and easy to understand (90.3%). Most respondents (91.7%) also found the message informative, with 53% strongly agreeing (See Table 2).

Message 2: Muscle Strengthening Exercises Recommendation: The draft message recommending the incorporation of muscle strengthening exercises saw the majority (74.4%) of respondents agree that the guideline was practical, with a large majority agreeing the message was clear and easy to understand (86.4%), with most respondents also finding the message clear and informative (82.5%).

Message 3: Incorporation of Pelvic Floor Exercises Recommendation: The draft message recommended pelvic floor exercises daily. Most respondents (85.6%) either agreed or strongly agreed that the message was practical, was clear (88.3%) and informative (87.7%).

Message 4: Incorporating Stretching and Functional Movement Recommendation: The draft message recommended considering functional mobility exercises in the weekly routine. The majority of pregnant and postpartum women who responded to the survey agreed or strongly agreed that the message was practical (75.8%), clear (80.0%) and informative (80.8%).

Message 5: Limiting Sedentary Time Recommendation: The draft message recommended limited time spent sitting or lying during the day. A large majority (80.2%) found the draft message in relation to sedentary behaviour to be practical. In addition, most (90.6%) found the message had good clarity and was informative (90.8%)

Message 6: Modifying Activity Recommendation: The draft message highlighted those with pregnancy complications may need to modify their physical activity. Similarly, to previous messages the majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the draft message was practical (78.6%), clear (84.3%) and informative (83.2%).

Message 7: Recognising Warning Signs Recommendation: The draft message identified the importance of recognising warning signs and described signs to stop physical activity. The majority

agreed or strongly agree that this draft message was practical (92.8%), clear and easy to understand (92.9%) and informative (94.4%).

In relation to the pregnancy messages, survey results indicated a strong consensus regarding the practicality, clarity, and informativeness of the messages. While the overall reception of the recommendations were positive, draft messages relating to muscle strengthening exercises and stretching and functional movement recommendations had relatively lower levels of agreement on practicality (74.4% and 75.8%, respectively). The lower practicality score suggested that respondents may have found these messages challenging to implement. Additionally, the modifying activity recommendation, while still positively received, had a slightly lower agreement on practicality (78.6%) compared to other messages. These observations indicate areas where further refinement was required for discussion at the National Stakeholder Meeting (Stage 4).

Table 2 Respondent ratings of perceived acceptability of messages for pregnancy

Message	Practicality	Clarity	Informativeness
1. General Recommendation	Strongly Disagree: 3.2% (n=8)	Strongly Disagree: 4.6% (n=12)	Strongly Disagree: 2.4% (n=6)
	Disagree: 7.2% (n=18)	Disagree: 3.9% (n=10)	Disagree: 3.6% (n=9)
	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 6.8% (n=17)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 1.2% (n=3)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 2.4% (n=6)
	Agree: 35.8% (n=90)	Agree: 26.2% (n=67)	Agree: 38.6% (n=98)
	Strongly Agree: 47.0% (n=118)	Strongly Agree: 64.1% (n=164)	Strongly Agree: 53.0% (n=134)
2. Muscle Strengthening Activity Recommendation	Strongly Disagree: 4.8% (n=12)	Strongly Disagree: 2.3% (n=6)	Strongly Disagree: 3.2% (n=8)
	Disagree: 12.0% (n=30)	Disagree: 7.4% (n=19)	Disagree: 9.1% (n=23)
	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 8.8% (n=22)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 3.9% (n=10)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 5.2% (n=13)
	Agree: 34.0% (n=85)	Agree: 33.1% (n=85)	Agree: 36.5% (n=92)
	Strongly Agree: 40.4% (n=101)	Strongly Agree: 53.3% (n=137)	Strongly Agree: 46.0% (n=116)
3. Pelvic Floor Recommendation	Strongly Disagree: 3.6% (n=9)	Strongly Disagree: 3.1% (n=8)	Strongly Disagree: 2.4% (n=6)
	Disagree: 5.2% (n=13)	Disagree: 4.3% (n=11)	Disagree: 6.8% (n=17)
	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 5.6% (n=14)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 4.3% (n=11)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 3.2% (n=8)
	Agree: 33.6% (n=84)	Agree: 25.4% (n=65)	Agree: 34.3% (n=86)
	Strongly Agree: 52.0% (n=130)	Strongly Agree: 62.9% (n=161)	Strongly Agree: 53.4% (n=134)
4. Stretching, Postural and Balance Exercises Recommendation	Strongly Disagree: 4.0% (n=10)	Strongly Disagree: 4.7% (n=12)	Strongly Disagree: 3.2% (n=8)
	Disagree: 13.7% (n=34)	Disagree: 8.2% (n=21)	Disagree: 10.8% (n=27)
	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 6.5% (n=16)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 7.1% (n=18)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 5.2% (n=13)
	Agree: 37.1% (n=92)	Agree: 34.5% (n=88)	Agree: 40.8% (n=102)
	Strongly Agree: 38.7% (n=96)	Strongly Agree: 45.5% (n=116)	Strongly Agree: 40.0% (n=100)
5. Limiting Sedentary Time Recommendation	Strongly Disagree: 2.8% (n=7)	Strongly Disagree: 3.1% (n=8)	Strongly Disagree: 1.6% (n=4)
	Disagree: 9.3% (n=23)	Disagree: 3.5% (n=9)	Disagree: 3.6% (n=9)
	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 7.7% (n=19)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 2.7% (n=7)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 4.0% (n=10)
	Agree: 24.6% (n=61)	Agree: 25.5% (n=65)	Agree: 31.9% (n=79)
	Strongly Agree: 55.6% (n=138)	Strongly Agree: 65.1% (n=166)	Strongly Agree: 58.9% (n=146)
6. Modification Recommendation	Strongly Disagree: 3.6% (n=9)	Strongly Disagree: 3.5% (n=9)	Strongly Disagree: 3.2% (n=8)
	Disagree: 6.5% (n=16)	Disagree: 7.5% (n=19)	Disagree: 8.8% (n=22)

Message	Practicality	Clarity	Informativeness
	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 11.3% (n=28) Agree: 28.6% (n=71) Strongly Agree: 50.0% (n=124)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 4.7% (n=12) Agree: 24.3% (n=62) Strongly Agree: 60.0% (n=153)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 4.8% (n=12) Agree: 28.8% (n=72) Strongly Agree: 54.4% (n=136)
	Strongly Disagree: 2.8% (n=7) Disagree: 2.0% (n=5)	Strongly Disagree: 3.5% (n=9) Disagree: 2.4% (n=6)	Strongly Disagree: 2.8% (n=7) Disagree: 1.2% (n=3)
7. Warning Signs Recommendation	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 2.4% (n=6) Agree: 23.2% (n=58) Strongly Agree: 69.6% (n=174)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 1.2% (n=3) Agree: 20.4% (n=52) Strongly Agree: 72.5% (n=185)	Neither Agree nor Disagree: 1.6% (n=4) Agree: 24.1% (n=60) Strongly Agree: 70.3% (n=175)

Pregnancy Messages Qualitative Responses

Participants from the target population (pregnant and postpartum women) were invited to share their views qualitatively via the online survey. Below is summary of key considerations highlighted by the respondents. Considerations outlined, as highlighted by the target population were presented at the National Stakeholder Meeting for discussion.

Need for Specific Examples and Practical Guidance (n=43)

Many respondents felt the guidelines were too general and lacked specific examples of exercises. Suggestions included breaking down exercises by trimester, providing sample workout plans, and detailing safe exercises for different stages of pregnancy. Including video or visual resources was also recommended.

"It would be helpful to know what not to do, or give examples of what is safe. Also breaking it down by trimester would be great."

"The guidelines are very generalised. I think some specific examples would help."

Clarification of Terminology and Detailed Explanations (n=18)

Respondents expressed confusion over certain terms, particularly "Kegel exercises," "moderate intensity," and specific muscle group exercises. They suggested including clearer definitions and explanations to make the guidelines accessible to individuals with varying levels of fitness knowledge.

"Some terms could be clarified—e.g., the terms 'Kegel exercises' and 'major muscle groups.'"

"Include explanations of what moderate intensity or strength exercises entail."

Inclusion of Professional Guidance and Support (n=27)

Many participants emphasised the need for support from qualified professionals like physiotherapists or prenatal fitness experts rather than relying solely on GPs or general healthcare professionals. They noted that healthcare providers often lack specific training in exercise during pregnancy and suggested incorporating specialist input.

"A health care provider isn't always accessible, and advice can be inconsistent."

Addressing Health Risks and Individual Circumstances (n=20)

Respondents wanted the guidelines to consider different health scenarios, such as high-risk pregnancies, severe nausea, or complications that limit physical activity. Including information for

previously active women on adapting their routines and for those who may need to reduce activity due to health concerns was seen as important.

"Guidelines should acknowledge those with high-risk pregnancies or those advised to rest."

"It's vital to consider those with complications like nausea, fatigue, or high-risk pregnancies."

Tone and Accessibility (n=15)

Some respondents felt the tone was prescriptive or "preachy" and suggested it should be more supportive and realistic, acknowledging the challenges that pregnant women face. They also recommended making the language simpler and incorporating visuals to improve accessibility, especially for those with lower literacy or non-native English speakers.

"The guidelines sound a bit preachy and could be more supportive."

"Make the message kinder. Not everyone can do high-intensity exercise during pregnancy."

Emphasis on Pelvic Floor and Core Exercises (n=12)

Other respondents highlighted the importance of pelvic floor health and felt that general guidance on Kegels was insufficient. They suggested adding instructions for proper technique and advising consultation with a women's health physiotherapist for specialised support.

"Pelvic floor exercises should be taught by trained professionals, not just general instructions."

"More detailed guidance on how to do Kegels and pelvic floor exercises is needed."

Desire for Emotional and Mental Health Support (n=8)

A subset of respondents wanted the guidelines to address the emotional and mental health benefits of exercise. They felt this would create a more holistic approach, acknowledging the challenges and pressures of pregnancy beyond physical health.

"There's little/no reference to mental health in these."

"The guidelines should acknowledge the psychological and emotional benefits of exercise."

Perceived Acceptability of Draft Messages for Postpartum

Consistent with data collected in relation to the draft messages for pregnancy, the target group were also presented with draft messages pertaining to the postpartum phase and invited to rate levels of acceptability across constructs practicality, clarity and informativeness.

Table 3 details the levels of acceptability (for each of the presented messages). The following is a summary of the findings (See Appendix 1 for draft guidelines and messages presented at this stage):

Message 1: General Postpartum Recommendation: The first message presented the general physical activity recommendation for postpartum women. Most respondents (75.0%) agreed that the presented iteration of the message was practical, with 45.7% strongly agreeing. For clarity, the majority reported the message as clear and easy to understand (85.12%), with 57.1% strongly agreeing. Most respondents (81.6%) also found the message informative, with 53.9% strongly agreeing.

Message 2: Muscle-Strengthening Recommendation: The draft message recommending the incorporation of muscle-strengthening exercises saw the majority (67.28%) of respondents agree that the guideline was practical, with 40.61% strongly agreeing. A large majority found the message clear and easy to understand (81.54%), with 48.21% strongly agreeing. Most respondents (73.33%) also found the message informative, with 41.21% strongly agreeing.

Message 3: Pelvic Floor Recommendation: The draft message recommended daily pelvic floor exercises. Most respondents (78.79%) either agreed or strongly agreed that the message was practical, with 53.94% strongly agreeing. The message was clear to 88.10% of respondents, with 63.10% strongly agreeing. Additionally, 82.42% found the message informative, with 56.97% strongly agreeing.

Message 4: Limiting Sedentary Time Recommendation: The draft message recommends limiting time spent sitting or lying during the day. The majority of postpartum women who responded to the survey agreed or strongly agreed that the message was practical (79.64%), with 47.90% strongly agreeing. For clarity, 88.03% found the message clear and easy to understand, with 57.49% strongly agreeing. Most respondents (85.63%) also found the message informative, with 56.29% strongly agreeing.

Table 3 Respondent ratings of perceived acceptability of postpartum messages

Message	Practicality	Clarity	Informativeness
1. General Postpartum Recommendation	Strongly disagree: 12 (7.32%)	Strongly disagree: 6 (3.57%)	Strongly disagree: 10 (6.13%)
	Disagree: 16 (9.76%)	Disagree: 13 (7.74%)	Disagree: 10 (6.13%)
	Neither agree nor disagree: 13 (7.93%)	Neither agree nor disagree: 6 (3.57%)	Neither agree nor disagree: 10 (6.13%)
	Agree: 48 (29.27%)	Agree: 47 (27.98%)	Agree: 45 (27.61%)
	Strongly agree: 75 (45.73%)	Strongly agree: 96 (57.14%)	Strongly agree: 88 (53.99%)
2. Muscle-Strengthening Recommendation	Strongly disagree: 10 (n=10, 6.06%)	Strongly disagree: 7 (n=7, 4.17%)	Strongly disagree: 11 (n=11, 6.67%)
	Disagree: 28 (n=28, 16.97%)	Disagree: 16 (n=16, 9.52%)	Disagree: 16 (n=16, 9.70%)
	Neither agree nor disagree: 16 (n=16, 9.70%)	Neither agree nor disagree: 8 (n=8, 4.76%)	Neither agree nor disagree: 17 (n=17, 10.30%)
	Agree: 44 (n=44, 26.67%)	Agree: 56 (n=56, 33.33%)	Agree: 53 (n=53, 32.12%)
	Strongly agree: 67 (n=67, 40.61%)	Strongly agree: 81 (n=81, 48.21%)	Strongly agree: 68 (n=68, 41.21%)
3. Pelvic Floor Recommendation	Strongly disagree: 9 (n=9, 5.45%)	Strongly disagree: 5 (n=5, 2.98%)	Strongly disagree: 7 (n=7, 4.24%)
	Disagree: 14 (n=14, 8.48%)	Disagree: 10 (n=10, 5.95%)	Disagree: 11 (n=11, 6.67%)
	Neither agree nor disagree: 12 (n=12, 7.27%)	Neither agree nor disagree: 5 (n=5, 2.98%)	Neither agree nor disagree: 11 (n=11, 6.67%)
	Agree: 41 (n=41, 24.85%)	Agree: 42 (n=42, 25.00%)	Agree: 42 (n=42, 25.45%)
	Strongly agree: 89 (n=89, 53.94%)	Strongly agree: 106 (n=106, 63.10%)	Strongly agree: 94 (n=94, 56.97%)
4. Limiting Sedentary Time Recommendation	Strongly disagree: 9 (n=9, 5.39%)	Strongly disagree: 4 (n=4, 2.40%)	Strongly disagree: 5 (n=5, 2.99%)
	Disagree: 17 (n=17, 10.18%)	Disagree: 9 (n=9, 5.39%)	Disagree: 12 (n=12, 7.19%)
	Neither agree nor disagree: 8 (n=8, 4.79%)	Neither agree nor disagree: 7 (n=7, 4.19%)	Neither agree nor disagree: 7 (n=7, 4.19%)
	Agree: 53 (n=53, 31.74%)	Agree: 51 (n=51, 30.54%)	Agree: 49 (n=49, 29.34%)
	Strongly agree: 80 (n=80, 47.90%)	Strongly agree: 96 (n=96, 57.49%)	Strongly agree: 94 (n=94, 56.29%)

In relation to the postpartum messages, survey results indicated overall consensus regarding the practicality, clarity, and informativeness of the messages. In line with the pregnancy messages, the overall reception of the recommendations was positive, yet draft messages relating to muscle-strengthening exercises had relatively lower levels of agreement on practicality (67.28%). Additionally, the general postpartum recommendation, while still positively received, had a slightly lower agreement on practicality (75.0%) compared to other messages. Guideline Message 3 (pelvic floor recommendation) received the highest levels of consensus across clarity, practicality, and informativeness. This indicated that respondents found this message the most straightforward and applicable. In addition, Guideline Message 4 (sedentary behaviour recommendation) had good consensus overall, but 20% of respondents were neutral or disagreed on practicality, indicating that some participants may find it challenging to implement consistently. These observations indicated areas where further refinement was required for discussion at the National Stakeholder Meeting (Stage 4).

Qualitative Responses on the Acceptability of Messages for Postpartum

To complement the quantitative findings, participants from the target population (pregnant and postpartum women) were also invited to share their views qualitatively via the online survey on the acceptability of the postpartum messages. Below is a summary of key considerations highlighted by the respondents. Considerations outlined, as highlighted by the target population were presented at the National Stakeholder Meeting for discussion.

1. Specificity and Clarity (N=40)

Guidelines were perceived as vague by some respondents and lacking practical examples or timelines, particularly for different types of delivery (vaginal vs. C-section).

"There's no mention of what's too much too soon, e.g., week 1 stick to 10 min walks, week 3 build up to 20 min walks."

"Guidelines should reference approximate timelines to guide mothers in the postpartum period."

2. Mental and Emotional Wellbeing (N=25)

Respondents reported the pressure to "bounce back" or achieve physical activity targets could feel overwhelming, unrealistic, and unsympathetic to reality of women. These statements were frequently referenced with emotional undertones.

"Postpartum is hard, and reading that you should do this and that feels like pressure on a new mother."

"The postpartum period is a vulnerable time... referring to 'losing weight' could be triggering for many."

3. Access to Professional Support (N=20)

Limited references to physiotherapists and structured postpartum exercise programmes were highlighted with a strong demand for physiotherapy and targeted professional input.

"Every woman should be assessed by a women's health physio before getting back to exercise."

"Guidelines without specific supports are not enough; women need access to postnatal physiotherapy."

4. Inclusivity and Practicality (N=18)

Respondents felt there needed to be acknowledgment of barriers such as time constraints, cost, and physical demands of caregiving. This was highlighted across different comments.

"Cost, time, and access to proper postpartum care are massive barriers."

"It's not very possible for physical activity during the day with a newborn if you choose to breastfeed and your partner only has two weeks of leave"

5. Types of Exercises (N=30)

There was an expressed need for detailed examples of safe exercises, particularly for muscle strengthening, pelvic floor recovery, and core rehabilitation. This was repeatedly emphasised, with specific suggestions for improvement.

"Women need specific advice re pelvic floor and more guidance on how to perform them."

"Examples of pram walking being considered 'moderate' help gauge what's realistic."

6. Delivery Specific Guidance (N=15)

Respondents highlighted the lack of differentiated advice for recovery after vaginal delivery vs. C-sections, which was mentioned explicitly by several respondents.

"Guidelines don't specifically address C-section births. We are forgotten."

"Separate advice for immediate 2-month periods following birth for vaginal vs. section."

Survey Consultation– Health, Social Care, Physical Activity and Sports Professionals

Health and social care professionals were also invited to provide insights on the guidelines. While the target population were presented with the messages to translate the guidelines, professionals were presented with a draft for both the pregnancy and postpartum guidelines that included: guidelines, good practice statements, specific population considerations, and messages for professionals. Professionals were invited to consult on all sets of guidelines (pregnancy, postpartum and chronic conditions).

Of the professionals who responded to the survey (n=148), 12.8% were male (n=19) and 85.8% were female (n=127) and 1.4% (n=2) preferred not to say. Respondents represented different health sectors who may utilise the physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for specific populations in their professional practice (See Table 4).

Table 4 Employment sectors of professional survey respondents

Employment Sector	N=	%
Health	89	59%
Physical activity/Sport	41	27%
Academia	9	6%
Other	13	8%
Total	148	

Respondents were also asked to rate the extent to which they would utilise the guidelines in their professional practice, of which 54.05% (n=80) indicated they would do so to a very large extent, 18.24% (n=27) to a large extent, 14.19% (n=21) to a moderate extent, 6.08% (n=9) to a small extent, and 7.43% (n=11) not at all.

As part of the separate but parallel process involving the development of physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for populations with chronic conditions, respondents were also given an option as to which population-based guidelines (pregnancy and postpartum or chronic conditions) they would like to respond to. Of these, 48.1% (n=74) selected people living with chronic conditions, 33.8% (n=50) selected pregnant and postpartum women and 20.3% (n=30) opted for both population groups.

Of the respondents to the professional survey n=80 (54.1%) responded in relation to the draft for pregnancy and postpartum. Respondents were requested to rate the clarity and appropriateness of

both sets (pregnancy and postpartum) of guidelines overall and as with the target population survey, to offer comments as to why they chose that rating. Respondents were also invited to rate the appropriateness of each good practice statement as well as each statement for specific populations, with room for qualitative feedback. Lastly, respondents rated the draft messages for professionals in relation to relevance, feasibility, support in delivering information, overall helpfulness and how likely they were to use them in practice, with commentary provided.

Professional Rating of Clarity and Appropriateness of Draft Pregnancy Guidelines

Respondents were asked to rate the clarity of the draft guidelines (See appendix 1 for draft guidelines circulated for feedback). The majority (82.1%) agreed or strongly agreed that the guidelines are clearly stated. A smaller proportion (12.5%) disagreed or strongly disagreed. Neutral responses accounted for 5.4%. In terms of appropriateness, most respondents (81.5%) agreed or strongly agreed that the guidelines are appropriate, showing a favourable view of their suitability. Only 7.4% disagreed or strongly disagreed (See Table 5).

Table 5 Professional rating of clarity and appropriateness of draft pregnancy guidelines

Pregnancy Guidelines	Strongly Agree N (%)	Agree N (%)	Neutral N (%)	Disagree N (%)	Strongly Disagree N (%)
Clarity	27 (37.5%)	25 (44.6%)	3 (5.4%)	3 (5.4%)	4 (7.1%)
Appropriateness	21 (38.9%)	23 (42.6%)	6 (11.1%)	2 (3.7%)	2 (3.7%)

Of the respondents who rated the clarity and appropriateness of the draft pregnancy guidelines, n=30 provided qualitative feedback which is summarised below:

1. Specificity and Tailoring of Guidelines (N=18)

Professionals emphasised the need for more detailed and tailored guidance, including specific exercises, intensity levels, and adaptations for different pregnancy and postpartum stages.

"More detail on the type of exercise... This might read better as bullet points, e.g., postural exercises aiming to support good alignment."

"Clarification on what moderate-intensity cardio is needed; could an RPE scale be used?"

"Guidelines are very baseline and don't really go into specific 'dos and don'ts.'"

They requested a need for actionable recommendations, including examples of strength and aerobic exercises, adaptations for various stages, and use of perceived exertion tools like the RPE scale.

2. Support for High-Intensity and Pre-Active Populations (N=12)

Some respondents felt that the guidelines do not sufficiently address the needs of women who were highly active before pregnancy or wish to maintain high-intensity workouts during pregnancy.

"Women who, before pregnancy, habitually engaged in vigorous-intensity aerobic activity... should continue these activities."

"A lot more women are training at a higher intensity; guidelines should be tailored to them as well."

Professionals advocated for including guidance for previously active populations, balancing safety with maintaining fitness levels.

3. Addressing Barriers and Risks (N=10)

Concerns about the potential pressure and risks posed by the guidelines for women with fatigue, medical conditions, or pregnancy complications were raised by some respondents.

"This statement provides a 'target'—this is dangerous as pregnant women may feel judged and upset if not able to achieve this target."

"Some women are prescribed bedrest; the statement to 'limit prolonged periods of sitting or lying down' is dangerous."

Professionals recommended that the guidelines should emphasise flexibility and provide alternative recommendations for women with medical complications or lower capacity for physical activity.

4. Professional Support and Training (N=8)

Respondents suggested that access to health professionals and the training of fitness providers creates a barrier to implementing the pregnancy guidelines effectively.

"Women should have access to a health professional in pregnancy to promote these guidelines specifically."

"GPs are not up to date on physical recommendations or how to modify exercise for complex pregnancies."

5. Balance of Rest and Activity (N=6)

Some professionals emphasised the importance of balancing activity with adequate rest, particularly during high-fatigue periods or in complicated pregnancies.

"Rest is important too; intensity needs to be monitored individually."

"Some pregnant women may feel pressure to exercise and risk overdoing it during critical recovery stages."

They highlighted how the guidelines should explicitly acknowledge the importance of rest and recovery alongside activity to avoid unintended pressure on women.

6. Communication and Clarity (N=6)

Respondents suggested that the guidelines should simplify messaging, avoid overly prescriptive language, and ensure accessibility for women with varying literacy levels.

"Guidelines need to address women who are physically inactive going into a pregnancy."

"Daily Kegels create an expectation that they must be done daily, which may not be appropriate for all clients."

Appendix 2 provides a link to the final published Guidelines.

Professional Rating of Appropriateness of Pregnancy Good Practice Statements

Respondents were asked to rate the perceived levels of appropriateness for each of the nine, draft good practice statements (See appendix 1 for draft Good Practice Statements presented for feedback). The majority of responses across all good practice statements were positive, with most respondents rating the statements as either appropriate or strongly appropriate (83.6%-100%), indicating high levels of perceived appropriateness overall (See Table 6).

Table 6 Professional respondents' appropriateness rating of pregnancy good practice statements

Good Practice Statement	Appropriateness Rating
1 Staying Active Safely Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 6.1% (n=3) Appropriate: 38.8% (n=19) Strongly appropriate: 53.1% (n=26)
2 Modification Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 4.1% (n=2) Appropriate: 32.7% (n=16) Strongly appropriate: 59.2% (n=29)
3 Complex Health Needs Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Appropriate: 44.9% (n=22) Strongly appropriate: 51.0% (n=25)
4 Safe Activities Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 4.1% (n=2) Appropriate: 36.7% (n=18) Strongly appropriate: 57.1% (n=28)
5 Activities to Avoid Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Appropriate: 24.5% (n=12) Strongly appropriate: 73.5% (n=36)
6 Considerations Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Appropriate: 30.6% (n=15) Strongly appropriate: 69.4% (n=34)
7 Activity at Work Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 6.1% (n=3) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 10.2% (n=5) Appropriate: 36.7% (n=18) Strongly appropriate: 46.9% (n=23)
8 Recognising Warning Signs Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Appropriate: 30.6% (n=15) Strongly appropriate: 69.4% (n=34)
9 Gauging Intensity Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 10.2% (n=5) Appropriate: 36.7% (n=18) Strongly appropriate: 51.0% (n=25)

Respondents were invited to provide comments on the good practice statements for pregnancy of which n=21 responded. A summary of key points is included below:

1. Tailoring Recommendations for Individual Needs and Trimesters (N=12)

Professionals stressed the importance of tailoring physical activity guidance based on the stage of pregnancy, individual fitness levels, and specific needs.

"No mention of various trimesters in any of these, which should be amended."

"Pregnant women may continue most forms of physical activity, but some will need modification."

"The stationary bike is appropriate for most women in earlier stages of pregnancy but potentially not later."

2. Support for High-Intensity Training and Pre-Pregnancy Fitness Levels (N=10)

Professionals also highlighted that woman accustomed to high-intensity training can safely continue with modifications and monitoring.

"High-intensity training is no longer deemed as dangerous for pregnant women."

"Women who trained at a high level can continue at a moderate-vigorous level until the 3rd trimester."

"Personally, I continued to train to vigorous but not max intensity and steadily reduced resistance training loads."

3. Clarity and Consistency in Messaging (N=8)

Some respondents found statements potentially contradictory or open to interpretation.

"The guideline is contradictory in places... Statements like 'women may continue most forms of physical activity' are potentially dangerous."

"The good practice statements should be clear and leave nothing open to interpretation."

4. Professional Support and Knowledge Gaps (N=7)

A lack of access to knowledgeable professionals for pregnant women was highlighted as a barrier to implementing the guidelines.

"I found it very hard to locate a health professional locally who had knowledge in training pregnant women."

"Consider discussing with a women's health physiotherapist or specialist if unsure."

5. Addressing Barriers and Risks (N=6)

Some comments emphasised the importance of mitigating risks, particularly around heavy lifting and overheating, while avoiding fear-based messaging.

"The statement above on avoiding heavy lifting should be supported by evidence... Many pregnant women already have children that they are lifting."

"Include a statement on how to gauge 'proper hydration' (guided by thirst) and avoiding overheating."

6. Terminology and Cultural Relevance (N=5)

A minority of respondents highlighted that some terminology, like "healthcare provider," was noted as inconsistent or culturally irrelevant in the Irish context.

"Use 'Registered' where health provider/professional is mentioned."

"'Provider' is a US term and may not be understood in Ireland."

Appendix 2 provides a link to the final Good Practice Statements.

Professional Rating of Appropriateness of Specific Population Statements for Pregnancy

Similarly, to the rating of the draft pregnancy good practice statements, professionals were invited to rate their perceived levels of appropriateness for Specific Population Statements (See appendix 1 for Specific Population Statements circulated for feedback). Across all specific population statements, a significant majority of respondents rated the statements as either appropriate or strongly appropriate, with agreement levels ranging from 83.6% to 100%. Statements about inactive populations received the highest consensus, with no disagreement and only 2% neutrality. The recommendations for highly active individuals and athletes showed slightly more neutral (8.5–11.1%) and inappropriate (2.0–2.1%) responses.

Table 7 Professional respondents' appropriateness rating of specific population statements for pregnant women

Specific Population Statement	Appropriateness Rating
1 Inactive Pregnant Women Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Appropriate: 53.1% (n=26) Strongly appropriate: 44.9% (n=22)
2 Active Pregnant Women Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2.1% (n=1) Inappropriate: 2.1% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 2.1% (n=1) Appropriate: 47.9% (n=23) Strongly appropriate: 45.8% (n=22)
3 Highly Active Pregnant Women Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Inappropriate: 2.0% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 10.2% (n=5) Appropriate: 40.8% (n=20) Strongly appropriate: 44.9% (n=22)
4 Pregnant Athlete Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2.1% (n=1) Inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 8.5% (n=4) Appropriate: 44.7% (n=21) Strongly appropriate: 44.7% (n=21)

Respondents also provided feedback on the draft Specific Population Statements within the pregnancy guideline document. A summary is provided below:

1. Support for Inactive Women (N=5)

Some respondents highlighted the need to include advice for inactive women, emphasising the importance of starting with light activities and integrating daily movement.

"Daily movement 'counts' for inactive women, e.g., walking to the shops, gardening, and should be encouraged."

"Inactive pregnant people should start with short bodyweight or light weights as walking is not enough to counteract changes during pregnancy."

2. Clarity and Specificity in Guidelines (N=6)

Some comments noted the statements are appropriate but too broad or non-specific, needing clearer guidance on safe and unsafe activities.

"All of these statements are appropriate but so broad and non-specific."

"More education needs to be provided to coaches or a general baseline of safe/unsafe activities relating to the gym provided on the HSE website."

3. Collaboration with Healthcare Providers (N=5)

Other professionals emphasised the need for consultation with appropriate healthcare professionals, especially for women engaging in vigorous training or with complex conditions.

"Consultation with healthcare provider in all circumstances involving vigorous training."

"Consider stating which healthcare providers are best placed to guide these women. Would an obstetrician have this knowledge? A midwife? A physiotherapist?"

4. Empowering Autonomy and Listening to the Body (N=3)

A minority of professionals suggested empowering pregnant women to make informed decisions and listen to their bodies while collaborating with healthcare professionals.

"Women usually know about their abilities, and we should empower them to be more autonomous and listen to their bodies."

5. Addressing Specific Conditions and Trimesters (N=4)

Some professionals called for tailored guidance for women with specific conditions (e.g., gestational diabetes, pre-eclampsia) and trimester-specific recommendations.

"Any additional guidance for those with gestational diabetes or pre-eclampsia?"

"Things can change quickly during pregnancy! What is appropriate at 3 months may not be appropriate at 4-9 months."

Appendix 2 provides a link to finalised Specific Population Statements.

In summary in relation to the pregnancy guidelines, good practice statements and statements for specific populations, most respondents from the professional cohort found the guidelines clear (82.1%) and appropriate (81.5%). High levels of appropriateness were also reported for the good practice and specific population statements, with agreement levels ranging from 83.6% to 100%. Qualitative feedback highlighted a desire for more specific guidance, recognition of the needs of highly active populations, clearer messaging, and sensitivity to rest, risk, and accessibility. Professionals commented on the value of tailored support, including trimester-specific considerations and collaboration with healthcare professionals. The actionable findings from this element of the

consultation were brought forward to the National Stakeholder Meeting to assist in informing refinement of the draft document for pregnancy.

Professional Rating of Clarity and Appropriateness of Postpartum Guidelines

Respondents were asked to rate the clarity of the guidelines overall. Clarity was highly rated among respondents in relation to the postpartum guidelines, where 83.0% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the guidelines were clearly stated. In relation to appropriateness 82.3% agreed or strongly agreed that the guidelines were appropriate, suggesting high levels of agreeableness with the clarity and appropriateness overall (see Table 8).

Table 8 Professional rating of clarity and appropriateness of draft postpartum guidelines

Postpartum Guidelines	Strongly Agree N (%)	Agree N (%)	Neutral N (%)	Disagree N (%)	Strongly Disagree N (%)
Clarity	44.7% (n=21)	38.3% (n=18)	8.5% (n=4)	8.5% (n=4)	0.0% (n=0)
Appropriateness	35.6% (n=16)	46.7% (n=21)	11.1% (n=5)	6.7% (n=3)	0.0% (n=0)

Respondents were also invited to add comments to these ratings. A summary is included below:

1. Importance of Individualised Recovery (N=8)

Some professionals emphasised that postpartum recovery should be tailored based on type of birth (e.g., vaginal vs. C-section), exercise history, and individual recovery pace.

"Postpartum needs to be more individualised based on birth, exercise experience, recovery, etc."

"Depends how long after postpartum, type of birth, and healing time."

2. Role of Women’s Health Physiotherapists (N=7)

A few professionals suggested women should visit a women’s health physiotherapist for pelvic floor assessments, core rehab, and individualised guidance.

"Recommend that women attend a pelvic health physio."

"Women should be directed to seek the guidance from women's health physios through their hospital or privately."

3. Early Postpartum Rest and Gradual Progression (N=6)

Some professionals noted the importance of rest during the initial weeks postpartum, followed by gradual reintroduction of light activities.

"Rest is important in the early weeks with gradual introduction of light rehab exercises."

"Profound rest is required in the first few weeks to heal alongside light intensity exercise."

4. Clarity on Exercise Recommendations and Examples (N=6)

Respondents requested clearer definitions of "light intensity" and specific examples of exercises, as well as timelines for postpartum activity progression.

"Light intensity needs to be qualified. Examples of strength exercises would be beneficial."

"No mention of specifics for C-section. This is needed."

5. Kegel Exercises and Pelvic Floor Health (N=5)

Some respondents raised concerns about blanket recommendations for Kegel exercises, suggesting they may not be appropriate for all women.

"Kegel exercises are not appropriate for all women and can create more issues."

"Pelvic floor exercises should be guided by a women's health physio."

6. Support Systems and Practical Considerations (N=4)

Professionals noted the need to address practical barriers such as time constraints, newborn care, and support systems for new mothers.

"No mention of support needed in order to get physical activity done with a newborn to care for."

Appendix 2 provides a link to the finalised guidelines.

Professional Rating of Appropriateness of Postpartum Good Practice Statements

Respondents were asked to rate the perceived levels of appropriateness for each of the eight, draft good practice statements (See appendix 1 for Good Practice Statements circulated for feedback). The majority of responses across all postpartum good practice statements were positive, with most respondents rating the statements as either appropriate or strongly appropriate (83.6%-100%; See Table 9). This indicates high levels of perceived appropriateness overall, reflecting high levels of perceived appropriateness by professional respondents for the statements.

Table 9 Professional respondents' appropriateness rating of postpartum good practice statements

Good Practice Statement	Appropriateness Rating
1 Transitioning Back to Activity Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 2.3% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 11.4% (n=5) Appropriate: 43.2% (n=19) Strongly appropriate: 43.2% (n=19)
2 Incorporating Aerobic Activity Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2.3% (n=1) Inappropriate: 2.3% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 6.8% (n=3) Appropriate: 40.9% (n=18) Strongly appropriate: 47.7% (n=21)
3 Activities to Avoid Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 4.4% (n=2) Appropriate: 44.4% (n=20) Strongly appropriate: 51.1% (n=23)
4 Water-Based Activities Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2.2% (n=1) Inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 11.1% (n=5) Appropriate: 37.8% (n=17) Strongly appropriate: 48.9% (n=22)
5 Activity While Breastfeeding Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 2.2% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Appropriate: 37.8% (n=17) Strongly appropriate: 60.0% (n=27)
6 Considerations Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Appropriate: 42.2% (n=19) Strongly appropriate: 57.8% (n=26)
7 Gauging Intensity Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 2.2% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 2.2% (n=1) Appropriate: 42.2% (n=19) Strongly appropriate: 53.3% (n=24)
8 Warning Signs to Cease Activity Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Appropriate: 40.0% (n=18) Strongly appropriate: 60.0% (n=27)

Respondents were invited to provide comments on the good practice statements for postpartum of. A summary of key points is included below:

1. Importance of Professional Guidance (n=8)

Consistent with the statements on the pregnancy guidelines, some professionals highlighted the need for postpartum-trained exercise specialists or pelvic health physiotherapists to guide women returning to physical activity.

“Specific mention to postpartum-trained exercise professionals being a first point of call.”

“GPs are not informed re returning to exercise, pelvic floor dysfunction, or basic exercises to strengthen core.”

2. Graded and Individualised Return to Exercise (n=7)

Others suggested placing emphasis on a gradual reintroduction to physical activity tailored to the individual's recovery stage and birth type.

“An emphasis on graded resistance training such as bodyweight exercises is essential.”

“Consideration of timelines for return to exercise (vaginal birth vs C-section).”

3. Healthcare Provider Roles and Clarifications (n=6)

Similarly, in the pregnancy guidelines feedback, there were some concerns about ambiguity in the guidelines regarding which healthcare professionals (e.g., GPs, physiotherapists, obstetricians) are equipped to provide clearance and advice.

“Consider stating the profession of healthcare providers who can give clearance.”

“Pelvic health physios should be included as key advisors in the postpartum period.”

5. Specific Guidelines for C-Section and High-Intensity Activities (n=5)

Some respondents, described a need for differentiated recommendations for caesarean and vaginal births, particularly for high-impact or intensive activities like running.

“Should mention more specific timelines – no high-intensity exercise/running for 12 weeks postpartum.”

“Guidance on C-section wound care and water-based activities is needed.”

5. Avoidance of Fear-Inducing Language (n=3)

A minority of respondents expressed concerns about phrasing that may create unnecessary fear among postpartum women.

“I wouldn’t say ‘until pelvic structures have stabilized’—this creates a sense of fear.”

6. Hydration and Hormonal Considerations (n=3)

Respondents highlighted the need for information on breastfeeding-related hormone effects and hydration during exercise.

“Return to exercise can be influenced by breastfeeding and its effects on hormones.”

7. Lack of Specificity and Practicality (n=5)

There were some comments on the broad and vague nature of statements, calling for timelines, detailed advice, and practical steps for implementation.

“The language is vague, with little detail on timelines and who can help.”

“It’s almost like this is telling us what to do but no guidance as to how to do it.”

Appendix 2 provides the link for the finalised Good Practice Statements.

Professional Rating of Appropriateness of Postpartum Specific Populations Statements

Similarly, to the rating of the draft postpartum good practice statements, professionals were invited to rate their perceived levels of appropriateness for Specific Population Statements (See appendix 1 for Specific Population Statements circulated for feedback). Statements about inactive postpartum women received the highest consensus, with no disagreement and only 6.7% neutrality. The recommendations for active women showed slightly more neutral (11.1%) and inappropriate (4.4%) responses. Highly active/athletes saw the most split responses, with 13.7% either uncertain or strongly inappropriate/inappropriate. Overall, the majority of responses across all specific population statements were positive, with most respondents rating the statements as either appropriate or strongly appropriate (83.6%-100%). This indicated high levels of perceived appropriateness by professional respondents (See Table 10 for full breakdown of responses).

Table 10 Professional respondents' appropriateness rating of specific population statements for postpartum women

Specific Population Statement	Appropriateness Rating
1 Inactive Populations Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Inappropriate: 2.2% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 6.7% (n=3) Appropriate: 44.4% (n=20) Strongly appropriate: 46.7% (n=21)
2 Active Populations Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2.2% (n=1) Inappropriate: 2.2% (n=1) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 11.1% (n=5) Appropriate: 42.2% (n=19) Strongly appropriate: 42.2% (n=19)
3 Highly Active/Athlete Populations Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2.3% (n=1) Inappropriate: 0.0% (n=0) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 11.4% (n=5) Appropriate: 47.7% (n=21) Strongly appropriate: 38.6% (n=17)

Respondents also provided feedback on the draft Specific Population Statements within the postpartum guideline document. A summary is provided below:

1. Need for Specialised Support and Guidance (n=6)

As with the pregnancy related feedback, some professionals emphasised the importance of postpartum women accessing pelvic floor physiotherapists or postnatal coaches with specific training.

"Women should be encouraged to see a pelvic floor physiotherapist and to seek a TRAINED postnatal coach... to help support mums adapt their core exercises, resistance, impact, etc., for their bodies."

2. Clarification on Timeframes and Progression (n=5)

Some respondents highlighted a lack of specific timelines and progression markers in the guidelines.

"There is no timeframe mentioned. There are no suggestions as to how to know it is safe to progress."

3. Individualised and Gradual Recovery Recommendations (n=4)

Professionals noted the importance of individualised plans based on the type of delivery, symptoms, and recovery rates.

"Need structured rehab and gradually build back to strength training and aerobic exercise regardless of previous fitness levels."

4. Collaboration with Healthcare Providers (n=3)

There were some suggestions for clearer identification of the healthcare professionals involved in postpartum exercise guidance, such as registered physiotherapists or consultants.

"State who the healthcare provider could be to guide this."

5. Pelvic Floor and Symptom Awareness (n=3)

A minority of comments underscored the need for clear guidance on pelvic floor health and symptoms indicating when progression should be paused or reconsidered.

"No pelvic floor guidance—such as leaking being an indication of not progressing to higher intensity exercises."

6. Avoiding Vague Terminology (n=3)

Some respondents criticised phrases like "fairly quickly" and "comfortable" for being too vague and potentially confusing.

"Fairly quickly is so vague—is it really helpful for a new mum?"

7. Awareness and Education for Healthcare Professionals (n=2)

As with the feedback related to the pregnancy draft, concerns were raised about the lack of knowledge among healthcare providers regarding postpartum physical activity.

"Healthcare providers are not adequately educated in this area, and I have heard non-appropriate advice being given."

Appendix 2 provides a link to the finalised Specific Population Statements.

In summary related to the postpartum guidelines draft, the guidelines appeared to be viewed by the professional respondents favourably overall with 83.0% agreeing or strongly agreeing they were clearly stated and 82.3% agreeing they were appropriate. The good practice statements were also positively received, with most statements rated as appropriate or strongly appropriate by over 83% of respondents. Comments supported gradual reintroduction to physical activity, clarity in guidance, and sensitivity to postpartum realities such as fatigue and breastfeeding. Similarly, the specific population statements received strong support, particularly for inactive populations (91.1% agreement). Qualitative feedback highlighted key themes including the importance of individualised recovery, the role of women's health professionals, and the need for clearer timelines, examples, and clarification of healthcare professional roles. Respondents emphasised the need for specialised

support, clearer progression markers, and consistent terminology. Actionable findings within the scope of the guidelines were brought forward to the National Stakeholder Meeting to assist in refinement of the guidelines.

Pregnancy and Postpartum Messages for Professionals

The last section of the online consultation for professionals was to invite respondents to rate the messages for health and social care and sport and physical activity professionals working with pregnant and postpartum women (See appendix 1 for messages circulated for feedback). Respondents were invited to rate the messages based on relevance, feasibility, support in delivering information, overall helpfulness and likelihood of use in practice. The majority of professionals found the messages relevant (98.5%) and reported that they were likely to use them in practice (98.5%). While the messages were seen as helpful overall (94.0%), a significant portion (40.6%) were neutral about their ability to support delivering information. The messages were largely seen as realistic and feasible (87.9%; See Table 11).

Table 11 Respondent ratings on the messages for health, social care, sport and exercise professionals

Criteria	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Relevance to Role	76.1% (n=51)	22.4% (n=15)	1.5% (n=1)	0.0% (n=0)	0.0% (n=0)
Realistic and Feasible to Apply	47.0% (n=31)	40.9% (n=27)	10.6% (n=7)	1.5% (n=1)	0.0% (n=0)
Support to Deliver Information	20.3% (n=13)	25.0% (n=16)	40.6% (n=26)	9.4% (n=6)	4.7% (n=3)
Overall Helpfulness	53.7% (n=36)	40.3% (n=27)	4.5% (n=3)	1.5% (n=1)	0.0% (n=0)
Likelihood of Use in Practice	58.2% (n=39)	40.3% (n=27)	1.5% (n=1)	0.0% (n=0)	0.0% (n=0)

Respondents were then invited to provide feedback on the messages for professionals. A minority (n=7), left comments which are summarised below:

- **Comments emphasised the need for more tailored advice for specific groups:**

“Highlight that there is a BJSM guideline to returning to running postpartum...encourage women to go see a pelvic floor physio.”

“Pregnant women with disabilities...should feature as part of all stages of the guidance.”

- **Plain English and accessibility:**

“Instead of ‘approximately 60% of women experience low back pain,’ state ‘three out of every five women can experience low back pain.’”

- **Suggestions for a broader approach to pelvic floor health:**

“Please include more about the variety of pelvic floor interventions, other than Kegels.”

Appendix 2 provides a link to finalised messages for professionals.

In summary, the messages for professionals were well received by the professional cohort overall, who reported a high likelihood of their use in practice. A significant proportion indicated neutrality in terms of the messages and their ability to support professionals to deliver information suggesting room for enhancing utility. However, the overall helpfulness of the messages was rated highly overall. Qualitative feedback from a small cohort of participants suggested more tailored messaging was required especially for subgroups of women along with clearer and more inclusive language. The findings from the online professional consultation were utilised in the National Stakeholder meeting (Stage 4) to refine the draft guidelines for pregnant and postpartum women.

Stage 4: National Stakeholder Meeting

The draft guidelines developed in Phase 1 and 2 and the stakeholder feedback gathered in Phase 3 were combined to form the basis of a National Stakeholder Meeting. The meeting took place in-person at a central location (i.e., Dublin) for accessibility and brought together stakeholders from across multiple sectors. Invitations were extended to a confined number of representatives from different stakeholder categories and to additional interested and relevant parties. Stakeholder mapping was performed with the HSE to identify the key bodies, organisations and professions to be represented. Stakeholders (n=30) representing the health sector, advocacy groups, academics and providers of pre- and post-natal physical activity were in attendance. The meeting included a morning session focused on the pregnancy and postpartum guidelines. The overall event was opened by the Chief Medical Officer. Following this, the pregnancy and postpartum session of the National Stakeholder meeting was opened by the National Clinical Director of the National Women and Infants Health Programme. This was followed by a presentation from the project team, which provided context on the development of the guidelines in terms of their purpose, structure and constraints. This was to focus discussions on refinement of the guidelines as opposed to broader discussions on structural barriers in physical activity promotion for pregnant and postpartum women. For example, while valid points were raised in the online consultation process in terms of accessibility and availability of exercise professionals for pregnancy and postpartum, this was not within the scope of the guidelines to address but was acknowledged as a broader recommendation. It was also clearly specified that the guidelines have a public health focus and would be constrained to broader recommendations as opposed to a detailed guide on exercise prescription or instruction. It was highlighted that the guidelines would also maintain alignment with the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines, 'Every Move Counts' and should maintain alignment with the guidelines under development for people living with chronic conditions.

Following on from this, stakeholders were presented with the process on the development of draft physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for pregnant and postpartum women addressing all phases outlined previously in this report (desk top review, evidence summary, project team review, stakeholder consultation). Stakeholders were then presented with a summary of the results from the online stakeholder consultation surveys outlined in Stage 3 of this report.

Informed by the development process up to this point, a series of round table discussion rounds with stakeholders and a moderator then took place as follows: 'Discussion round 1' focused on the pregnancy guidelines and messaging with a focus on three key objectives; Enhancing Clarity and Specificity; Tone and Accessibility; and Inclusivity. 'Discussion round 2' addressed the postpartum

guidelines and messaged and also focused on three tailored key objectives relevant to that section; Clarity and Practicality; Tone and Balance; and Inclusivity. Finally, ‘Discussion round 3’ focused on messages for professionals and addressed the following objectives; Supportive Guidance; Consistency Across Professional Groups; and Scope of Recommendations.

Following on from this, a summary of recommendations and further discussion points were collated. These were fed back to the stakeholder groups. Where possible issues raised that required clarity were addressed at the meeting by members of the project team and recommendations were taken back to the working group for further refinement of the guidelines. Table 12 outlines a summary of the recommendations and outcome.

Table 12 Summary of national stakeholder consultation meeting recommendations and response

Discussion Round 1: Pregnancy Guidelines and Messaging	
Recommendation from stakeholders	Outcome
Include examples of muscle strengthening activity	Weak evidence available to recommend safe muscle-strengthening exercises for pregnancy within scope of population-level public health guidelines.
Safety of supine exercises should be considered	Statement included in refined draft on limiting and modifying supine position during pregnancy in the event of symptoms based on other international guidelines.
*Include trimester specific guidelines	*Not included in the refined draft due to the limitations in the strength and consistency of available evidence to support distinct recommendations by trimester within the scope of population-level public health guidelines.
Add clarity to message 4 – postural and functional exercises	Message 4 was merged with the message on muscle-strengthening exercises to streamline recommendations and better articulate their collective benefits, as part of a broader, accessible strengthening approach
*Exercises should include signposting to physiotherapist	*While the value of physiotherapy support was acknowledged, universal signposting to physiotherapists was not included in the final guidelines. This decision reflects the scope and accessibility limitations of public health guidance, where equitable access to specialised services such as physiotherapy cannot be assumed. Instead,

	the guidelines emphasise that women with complications or specific needs should seek advice from an appropriate healthcare professional, allowing for flexibility based on individual circumstances and available resources.
Consider the emphasis on Kegels within pelvic floor muscle training (PFMT)	Guidelines were refined to prioritise pelvic floor exercises with 'Kegels' used as an example rather than emphasised. The revised language supports informed choice and better reflects the diversity of effective PFMT approaches.
Place less emphasis on weight management	Reference to weight management was retained due to its relevance as one of several health outcomes supported by physical activity. However, it has been deemphasised and refined for tone presenting weight management within a broader context of overall maternal and fetal health.
Consider placing emphasis on mental health	Mental health has been given greater prominence across both the pregnancy and postpartum guidelines. The refined drafts explicitly reference benefits such as reduced risk of depression, improved mood, stress management, and better sleep, positioning mental health as a central and recurring benefit of physical activity.
Provide an explanation for the different types of intensity (e.g. light, moderate, vigorous)	A glossary of key terms has been included in the refined guideline documents. This glossary provides plain-language explanations and examples of light-, moderate-, and vigorous-intensity activities, with reference to tools such as the Rate of Perceived Exertion (RPE) scale.
Clearer instructions needed for pelvic floor exercises	A more detailed explanation of pelvic floor exercises has been added to the glossary section of the guidelines. While the document is not intended to serve as a "how-to" guide, this addition provides greater clarity on what pelvic floor exercises entail, including its purpose and common techniques (e.g., Kegels). The benefits of pelvic floor exercises are emphasised in the messages for both pregnancy and postpartum.

Discussion Round 2- Postpartum Guidelines and Messaging

Messaging should be tailored to delivery type (caesarean section vs vaginal delivery)	*While the guidelines acknowledge the differing recovery experiences between caesarean (C-section) and vaginal deliveries, they do not provide separate, tailored messages for each delivery method. This is for key reasons; the guidelines are designed to offer broad, evidence-based recommendations applicable to the general population; creating distinct messages for each delivery type could complicate the guidelines and potentially reduce their clarity and applicability; recovery experiences can vary widely among individuals, even within the same delivery method and tailoring messages to specific delivery methods would not address this variability; not all individuals have access to specialised postpartum care or resources.
Emphasise the importance of rest and recovery	The guidelines have been refined to emphasise the need for rest and recovery during postpartum. By prioritising rest and gradual reintroduction of physical activity, the guidelines aim to support a holistic approach to postpartum recovery.
Include a message about rest before messaging on sedentary behaviour	Reference to rest and recovery was incorporated in the guidelines and messaging related to sedentary behaviour. This aims to provide a more empathetic and non-judgmental tone.
Give a timeline of when to expect to return to physical activity based on delivery type	As with point 1, specific timelines for resuming physical activity postpartum or based on delivery type are not included in the guidelines. Recovery varies significantly and prescribing uniform timelines do not accommodate this variability. Women are advised to consult with a healthcare professional if they have concerns on readiness to resume various activities considering factors such as delivery type, complications and overall health status.
Tone should be gentle and compassionate but direct also	The messaging tone has been refined to balance empathy with clarity.

Highlight importance of women making time for themselves	The guidelines and messaging have been refined to emphasise the need for rest and recovery within the context of physical activity and underscore the significance of women dedicating time to their well-being.
Don't signpost to specific health care professionals (GP and public health nurse should act as gatekeepers)	Given limitations and variability in access to specialised care, generalising to a primary healthcare professional promotes an accessible pathway to support.
Consider mentioning going to prenatal classes in the community	Community-based resources, such as prenatal classes, can offer valuable support; however, the guidelines focus on universally applicable and inclusive recommendations and encourage professionals to inform women about available local resources.
Weight loss messaging shouldn't be emphasised	As with the pregnancy guidelines, the postpartum guidelines have been refined to mention, but not emphasise, references to weight management. The guidelines prioritise overall health and well-being over weight loss, aligning with a holistic approach to postpartum recovery.
Mental wellbeing as a barrier to physical activity should be addressed	The refined guidelines have been updated to highlight the mental health benefits of physical activity. While they do not explicitly discuss mental health challenges as barriers, the guidelines underscore how regular physical activity can enhance mental wellbeing reflecting the scope of public health guidelines.
Normalise 'wobbly' days and fluctuations in recovery during postpartum.	While not directly incorporated, refinement to the guidelines aim to encompass a more empathetic and non-judgemental tone where the essence of this sentiment is embedded within the existing messaging that emphasises rest and gradual recovery.
Kegel recommendations as per pregnancy guidelines above (emphasis on Kegel exercises)	As per the refinement to the pregnancy guidelines, the refinement to the postpartum guidelines means pelvic floor exercises are recommended with Kegel exercises mentioned as a common example rather than emphasised.

Physical activity above light intensity should be included in sedentary behaviour messaging.	In the context of sedentary behaviour, the guidelines emphasise that any intensity (including light intensity) provides health benefits in line with Every Move Counts. Light intensity is not emphasised as the only intensity.
Early postpartum physical activity should be low impact.	The guidelines recommend initiating light-intensity physical activity postpartum and progressing gradually, allowing for individualised recovery.
Need more information for contraindications based on delivery type	General guidance is provided within the guidelines for contraindications. The guidelines advise consulting healthcare professionals for personalised advice, especially in cases of complications or specific delivery types.
Messaging on postpartum depression should be included	The guidelines highlight that physical activity can reduce the risk of postpartum depression and improve mood and emotional well-being.
Warning signs should be included as per pregnancy	Warning signs to cease physical activity during postpartum are included in the good practice statements. The guidelines list warning signs to cease activity, such as heavy vaginal bleeding or pain that doesn't subside with rest and advise consulting a healthcare professional if these occur.
Pregnancy and Postpartum guidelines should mirror each other	Respectful of the nuances between pregnancy and postpartum stages, efforts have been made to align the structure and messaging of both guidelines.
Consistent wording recommended e.g. 'Should be incorporated' vs 'Should aim'	Language throughout the guidelines has been reviewed and standardised to ensure clarity and consistency.
Should be a slow start and build up to pelvic floor exercises	The guidelines recommend initiating pelvic floor exercises in the early postpartum period and gradually increasing intensity as appropriate.

Discussion Round 3: Messages for Professionals

Pregnancy should be framed as a normal transition rather than a condition.	The guidelines underscore that pregnancy and postpartum are natural life stages, highlighting the benefits of physical activity during these periods. The messaging aims to normalise physical activity during these life stages with the aim of empowering these populations.
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Exercises should be emphasised as safe.	The messaging underscores that physical activity is safe and beneficial for most pregnant and postpartum women. They aim to dispel myths and encourage women to engage in appropriate physical activity.
Messages can be more scientific for professionals.	Cognisant of multiple audiences, the refined guidelines aim to balance evidence-based terminology with inclusive language.
It should be captured in the messages that exercises should be discussed from the moment pregnancy occurs.	Healthcare professionals are encouraged to discuss physical activity from the onset of pregnancy in the refined messaging.
Healthcare providers can be cautious in delivering information as it could be challenged.	The guidelines aim to provide clear messaging and information to support professionals.
Use images that are representative of the Irish mother.	It is acknowledged that inclusive imagery ensures relatability and encourages engagement across different demographics. This recommendation can be brought forward at design stage, while aligning to the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines 'Every Move Counts'.
Accessible examples such as walking, pushing a pram, baby in sling, loading car with shopping could be added.	These examples are included in the refined guidelines to illustrate practical and feasible activities to assist women in identifying opportunities for incorporating activity into daily life.
Address the anxiety that might accompany early postpartum	This is underscored in messages to professionals which outline the mental health benefits of staying active during postpartum with even small increases or light-intensity activities.
Avoid the term 'patients'.	Guidelines have been refined to remove reference to the term 'patients'.
Get Active Questionnaire for pregnancy should be used.	The recommendation to incorporate the "Get Active Questionnaire for Pregnancy" (GAQ-P) into the national public health guidelines was acknowledged. The national public health guidelines aim to offer broad, universally applicable recommendations suitable for the general

	population, without the need for individualised screening tools.
Rate of Perceived Exertion (RPE) is not appropriate for pregnancy.	*Reference to RPE remained within the guidelines as the evidence-base highlights that RPE provides a more consistent measure of intensity during pregnancy. It allows women to self-monitor their exertion levels based on how they feel, which can be more intuitive and safer. The RPE scale is flexible and can be adjusted to individual fitness levels and pregnancy stages where heart rate responses to exercise can be unpredictable due to physiological changes.
Include messages on importance of rest and recovery in post-partum period.	The guidelines have been refined to place further emphasis on the need for rest and recovery as previously outlined.
Messages on 'myths' should be included earlier for professionals.	This message has been amended to appear as the first message to professionals in the guidelines.
Consider adding some examples.	Examples of safe exercises, recommended activities, exercises to avoid, contraindications and warning signs are embedded throughout the guidelines.
Balancing exercises should also be included in these messages.	Balancing exercises are mentioned within the guidelines and are now included within the glossary to provide a definition.
Guidelines should mirror Every Move Counts professional section.	Respectful of the nuances across specific populations, these guidelines will be aligned to the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines 'Every Move Counts' to promote consistency and continuity of care.
Should signpost to evidence-based resources rather than healthcare professionals.	The guidelines do not include direct signposting to specific evidence-based resources. The primary objective of public health guidelines is to provide overarching recommendations that are broadly applicable. Directing individuals to specific resources falls more appropriately within the remit of healthcare professionals, who can offer personalised advice based on individual needs and the most current evidence.

Other Discussion Points	
Consider guidelines for policy makers highlighting access to education/training for healthcare professionals, access gaps, postnatal hubs, existing structures, leadership and management.	In response to this discussion point the refined guidelines were updated to include an additional section on messages for policy and decision makers.
The healthcare professional reference in the guidelines is broad. More guidance and education for the healthcare professional is needed working with pregnancy and postpartum women where a lack of professional training in this space is a barrier.	The refined pregnancy and postpartum physical activity guidelines acknowledge the importance of healthcare professional training in supporting women during these periods. However, the development and implementation of specific training programmes for healthcare professionals fall outside the scope of these guidelines. This has been incorporated into the messages for policy and decision makers.
Consider the importance of additional resources (e.g., guidebook)	The recommendation to develop additional resources to support pregnancy and postpartum physical activity was acknowledged. While this is beyond the scope of the guidelines, the recommendation to develop educational resources has been added to the messages for policy makers.
Consider micro credentials for professionals	This falls outside the scope of the public health guidelines. Can be brought forward as a recommendation.
Consider opportunities to build capacity within existing groups e.g., MECC, CSPs, Sport Ireland.	While this is also outside the scope of the guidelines, building capacity of healthcare professionals for pregnancy and postpartum physical activity has been incorporated in the messages for policy and decision makers within the guidelines.
*Overarching recommendations which were addressed at the meeting by a member of the project team	

Stage 5: Consolidation and Refinement

The project team considered findings from the National Stakeholder Meeting and subsequent feedback from the HSE Healthy Eating Active Living Programme team before agreeing the final draft guidelines and messages. Table 12 above outlines the rationale for some key amendments. The project team also disaggregated more complex messages and re-ordered messages and statements in other sections. A notable addition to the guidelines were messages for policy and decision makers included to reflect broader level recommendations from stakeholders to support the implementation of the guidelines. These are outlined in appendix 2.

At final draft stage, the project team were tasked with identifying the messages recommended for prioritisation from the full set of messages published in Appendix 2. Table 13 outlines the ranking of these prioritised messages. In summary, most useful messages within the messages for pregnant women were related to direct benefits for baby's health and clear, actionable pelvic-floor guidance. For the messages for postpartum women, those relating to mental-health and recovery were prioritised followed by pelvic-floor routines and gradual activity re-introduction. The project team saw myth-dispelling and the opportunity for behaviour change when motivation is heightened during pregnancy and postpartum, as top messages for health and social care professionals, with warning-signs and early postpartum benefits jointly third. The 'every move counts' concept and clear health outcomes message were equally prioritised for exercise professionals, with physiological considerations second and general prescription principles and opportunities to be active with baby sharing third place (see Table 13).

Table 13 Ranking of messages by the project team

Message type	Top 3 Messages (Ranked by usefulness)
Messages for Pregnant Women	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Baby's Health: For your baby, staying active supports healthy growth and reduces the risk of excessive birth weight and the risk of obesity and related metabolic problems later in life.2. Pelvic Floor Routine: You should aim to incorporate pelvic floor exercises into your daily routine throughout your pregnancy stages to prevent urinary incontinence and support postpartum recovery. If you have any concerns about how to perform them correctly or experience discomfort, consult your healthcare professional, but in

most cases, these exercises are safe and beneficial for all pregnant women

3. **Benefits of Pelvic Floor Exercises:** Regular pelvic floor exercises help strengthen the pelvic floor muscles, and can help prevent or reduce urinary incontinence, support your pelvic organs during pregnancy, and promote faster recovery after childbirth.

**Messages for
Postpartum
Women**

1. **Recovery and Mental Health:** Physical activity helps you recover, improves your mood, and promotes better sleep. Staying active can also reduce your risk of postpartum depression, aid your physical recovery and improve your overall well-being.
2. **Pelvic Floor Exercises:** Pelvic floor exercises should be incorporated into your daily routine. Aim to do them daily and consult a healthcare professional or exercise professional if you have any concerns.
3. **Gradual progression:** You should aim to be physically active during your postpartum recovery. Start with light-intensity activities, like walking, and gradually build up to moderate-intensity physical activity. Consult your healthcare professional if you had complications during delivery.

**Messages for
Health and Social
Care
Professionals**

1. **Myth dispelling:** Myths about physical activity being harmful to pregnant and postpartum women should be dispelled. Healthcare professionals should emphasise that physical activity is not only safe but beneficial for most pregnant women and can be adapted to suit their specific health needs and abilities.
2. **Opportunity for behaviour change:** Regular physical activity during pregnancy and postpartum reduces the risk of gestational diabetes, pre-eclampsia, and postpartum depression, helps manage weight, promotes better sleep and mood and enhances postpartum recovery. Encourage women to stay active even with small increases in physical activity or light-intensity activities.

3. (Joint) Warning signs: Pregnant women should be informed by their healthcare professional of the danger signs alerting them as to when to stop; or to limit physical activity and consult a qualified health-care professional immediately should they occur.

And

Postpartum benefits: In the early postpartum phase, staying active improves mood, reduces the risk of postpartum depression, helps restore physical strength, and aids in regaining functional movement for daily tasks, including caring for the baby.

**Messages for
Sport and
Physical Activity
Professionals**

1. (Joint) Every Move Counts: Recent evidence demonstrates that there is no minimum amount of physical activity required to achieve some health benefits. Aiming to do even 10 minutes of activity at a time can be effective as a behavioural goal for pregnant and postpartum women starting from low levels of activity.

And

Health outcomes: Regular physical activity during pregnancy and postpartum reduces the risk of gestational diabetes, pre-eclampsia, and postpartum depression, helps manage weight, promotes better sleep and mood and enhances postpartum recovery. Encourage women to stay active even with small increases in physical activity or light-intensity activities.

2. Anatomical Changes: Pregnancy results in significant anatomical and physiological changes, such as weight gain, a shift in the centre of gravity, and increased forces across joints. These factors should be considered when recommending exercise to pregnant women.

3. (Joint) Prescription principles: The principles of exercise prescription for pregnant women do not differ from the general population. Most pregnant women can exercise safely, provided they receive appropriate guidance and modifications as necessary.

And

Active with Baby: Opportunities for women to be active with their babies can help empower women to embrace physical activity not

only for their health, but also as a means of nurturing their relationship with their babies.

Lastly, the National Women and Infants Programme in the HSE then completed a document review and provided a foreword for clinical programme endorsement. Following this, the finalised documents were submitted to the HSE for design. These, the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland for Pregnant and Postpartum Women, are available via the link in Appendix 2.

Conclusions

This report outlines the process of extending the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland 'Every Move Counts', to include guidance for pregnant and postpartum women. The development of these guidelines represents a significant advance in inclusive public health policy. Through a rigorous process of comprehensive evidence synthesis, project team review, wide-ranging stakeholder consultation, national stakeholder meeting and iterative refinement, these guidelines have been shaped by the best available evidence and the lived experiences of pregnant and postpartum women and professionals.

Key strengths include clear, actionable recommendations that acknowledge differences in health status, physical activity level, and context; balanced messaging that promotes both activity and rest; and explicit attention to safe practice across pregnancy stages and postpartum recovery. Although specificity around timelines and exercise modalities are moderated to maintain a public health scope, these guidelines aim to achieve balance between supportive messages and clarity for pregnant and postpartum women as well as health, social care, physical activity and sports professionals. It is noteworthy that separate guidelines and messages have been developed for pregnant and postpartum women, respecting the distinct physiological stages and lived experiences of women before and after birth. The addition of messages for policy and decision makers also aims to advocate for the resources and capacity building required to support and empower pregnant and postpartum women to be safely physically active. Moving forward, their successful implementation will depend on effective dissemination, ongoing evaluation, and the development of supportive resources. By embedding these guidelines into clinical practice, community programmes, and national health promotion strategies, stakeholders including individuals, communities, health systems and government can support women's safe, effective and equitable engagement in physical activity throughout the maternity journey, where every move counts.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Draft Pregnancy and Postpartum Guidelines and Messages Circulated for Stakeholder Consultation

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The National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland: Pregnant and Postpartum Women – **Draft Guidelines and Messaging for Consultation**

Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Pregnancy

These guidelines are for all pregnant women irrespective of age, fitness level, previous physical activity, health status or cultural background. Engaging in physical activity during pregnancy is generally safe and beneficial for both mother and baby. Staying active can help to reduce the risk of; pre-eclampsia, gestational hypertension, gestational diabetes, excessive gestational weight gain, low back pain and delivery complications among others, while also promoting improved mental health, reduced stress and better sleep. Physical activity can also benefit your baby by supporting healthy growth and development, reducing the likelihood of excessive birth weight, as well as metabolic disorders in childhood and adulthood. Limiting the time spent sitting or lying down for prolonged periods can also reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease, cancer and type-2 diabetes. Whether pregnant women are starting from a sedentary background, are active, highly active, or have specific health considerations, there are safe and appropriate ways to stay active. Pregnant women should always consult their healthcare providers if they have concerns, particularly in the case of a high-risk pregnancy or specific conditions. Every move counts- it's important to start at an appropriate level and progress at an individual pace.

Guidelines:

It is recommended that:

- All pregnant women without contraindication should undertake regular physical activity throughout their pregnancy.
- Women with complex health needs should modify the type and intensity under the supervision of a healthcare provider. There are few contraindications that limit physical activity completely.
- Pregnant women should aim to be active on most, if not all days of the week. Aim for at least 2 hours and 30 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic activity spread throughout the week, for substantial health benefits.
- Pregnant women should incorporate a variety of aerobic and muscle-strengthening activities throughout the week. Gentle stretching, postural, functional and balance exercises may also be beneficial.
- All pregnant women should incorporate pelvic floor muscle exercises (Kegel exercises) daily.

It is recommended that:

- All pregnant women should limit prolonged periods of sitting or lying down during waking hours and avoid extended periods of inactivity. Replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity) provides health benefits.

Good Practice Statements

Most pregnant women can be active safely and there are few contraindications in which physical activity should be limited. Pregnant women should consult a healthcare provider if contraindications are present.

Pregnant women may continue most forms of physical activity during pregnancy although some forms will require modification.

Women with complex health needs should modify the type and intensity under the supervision of a healthcare provider.

Activities such as walking, swimming, stationary cycling, low-impact aerobics, modified yoga and Pilates, running/jogging, resistance exercises, stretching exercises and water-based exercises are safe and beneficial for most pregnant women.

Pregnant women should avoid participating in activities which involve physical contact that can increase risk of abdominal trauma (e.g., basketball, rugby and football); activities which involve a high risk of falling (e.g., horse riding and skiing); activities with changes in barometric pressure (e.g., scuba diving) and prolonged activities in excessive heat or humid conditions.

Pregnant women should ensure proper hydration, avoid overheating, and wear non-restrictive clothing including appropriate shoes and a supportive bra.

While staying active at work is encouraged, pregnant women should avoid prolonged heavy lifting or strenuous physical tasks.

All pregnant women, their healthcare providers and exercise professionals should be aware of the warning signs to cease activity such as; persistent dizziness, excessive shortness of breath before physical exertion, chest pain, painful uterine contractions, vaginal bleeding, loss of fluid from the vagina or severe headache. They should consult a qualified healthcare provider immediately such warning signs occur.

The 'talk test' is a simple and effective method to gauge moderate intensity physical activity during pregnancy, if trying to remain in the moderate zone. During moderate-intensity exercise, pregnant women should be able to carry on a conversation but not sing.

Specific Population Considerations

Inactive: Pregnant women who were inactive prior to pregnancy should start gradually with light-intensity activities such as walking or water-based exercises and aim to build up to at least 2 hours and 30 minutes of moderate-intensity activity per week. Begin with short sessions (10 to 15 minutes), gradually increasing the duration as fitness improves.

Active: Pregnant women who were engaging in regular physical activity pre-pregnancy should continue with at least 2 hours and 30 minutes to 5 hours of moderate-intensity aerobic activity per week, spread throughout the week. If comfortable, pregnant women can include vigorous-intensity activities, adjusting the intensity based on fatigue, comfort, and the progress of the pregnancy and in consultation with a healthcare provider as needed.

Highly active/athletes: Pregnant women engaging in regular vigorous physical activity pre-pregnancy, are generally safe to continue as long as it feels comfortable. Aim for 2 hours and 30 minutes to 5 hours of vigorous-intensity aerobic activity spread throughout the week.

Pregnant **athletes** who were engaging in vigorous or high intensity exercise prior to pregnancy can generally continue with their training, as long as adjustments are made to accommodate the physical changes of pregnancy. Advice on training activities should be sought at first consultation with a healthcare provider.

Messages

1. You should aim to stay physically active throughout your pregnancy. For most pregnant women regular physical activity is safe and beneficial for both you and your baby. (what)

- Physical activity during pregnancy can help you maintain a healthy weight, reduce the risk of complications like gestational diabetes and pre-eclampsia, improve your mood, prevent lower back pain and help you sleep better, among other benefits. For your baby, staying active supports healthy growth and reduces the risk of excessive birth weight and the risk of obesity and related metabolic problems later in life. (why)
- Aim for at least 2 hours and 30 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic activity per week. Try to be active on most days for the week. If you have complex health needs or a high-risk pregnancy, work with your healthcare provider to adjust the type and intensity of your activity. There are very few conditions that prevent physical activity entirely, so find a way to move that works for

you. Even light intensity activity such as housework, light gardening and walking for errands can have health benefits.

2. In addition to aerobic activity, you should aim to include muscle-strengthening exercises as part of your weekly routine. (what)

- Strengthening your muscles can help support your body during pregnancy, improves posture, and prepares you for childbirth and recovery. It also helps with daily activities like lifting and carrying your baby after birth and can reduce the risk of injury, discomfort and pain, especially back and pelvic pain. (why)
- Aim to do muscle-strengthening exercises throughout the week. Focus on exercises that target major muscle groups. If you're unsure about what exercises are safe, consult your healthcare provider (how)

3. Regardless of your fitness level or pregnancy stage, you should aim to incorporate pelvic floor exercises (commonly known as Kegel exercises) into your daily routine. (what)

- These exercises help strengthen the pelvic floor muscles, which support your bladder, uterus, and bowel. Regular pelvic floor exercises can help prevent or reduce urinary incontinence, support your pelvic organs during pregnancy, and promote faster recovery after childbirth. (why)
- Kegel exercises are simple and can be done anywhere. Aim to do them daily by contracting and relaxing the muscles that stop the flow of urine. If you have any concerns about how to perform them correctly or experience discomfort, consult your healthcare provider, but in most cases, these exercises are safe and beneficial for all pregnant women. (how)

4. Consider adding stretching, postural, functional and balance exercises to your weekly routine. (what)

- These types of exercises can help reduce discomfort such as lower back pain, improve mobility and support your body through the changes of pregnancy. (why)
- These activities may require modification due to normal changes in your body during pregnancy, including how you move and balance, which may increase risk of falls, discomfort or injury. (how)

5. You should aim to limit the time spent sitting or lying down during the day as prolonged sedentary behaviour leads to health risks. (what)

- Staying active, even with light movement, helps reduce the risks associated with sitting or lying down for long periods. This can lower your chances of developing serious health issues like cardiovascular disease, diabetes or depression (why)

- Try to break up long periods of sitting or lying down by standing, walking, or stretching regularly throughout the day. (how)

6. If you have a medical condition or pregnancy complication, physical activity may need to be modified or in some cases, restricted, under the guidance of a healthcare provider. (what)

- If you need to restrict your activity, it's still important to avoid excessive inactivity. (why)
- Your healthcare provider or exercise professional can guide you on safe movements or light activities you can do. (how)

7. While staying active is beneficial during pregnancy, it's crucial to listen to your body and recognise warning signs that indicate when to stop or limit physical activity. (what)

- All women and their health and exercise professionals should be aware of the warning signs to cease activity such as; persistent dizziness, excessive shortness of breath, chest pain, painful uterine contractions, vaginal bleeding, loss of fluid from the vagina or severe headache.
(why/how)

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Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Postpartum

These guidelines are for all postpartum women, regardless of delivery type, fitness level, previous physical activity, health status or cultural background. Engaging in physical activity after childbirth is generally safe and beneficial for recovery and long-term well-being. Physical activity can help reduce the risk of postpartum depression, improve sleep, and support healthy weight management. Physical activity also promotes faster recovery from delivery and strengthens the muscles used in caregiving tasks. Limiting the time spent sitting or lying down for prolonged periods can also reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease, cancer and type-2 diabetes. Whether a vaginal or caesarean delivery or a woman was active during pregnancy or not, there are safe ways to get moving again. Postpartum women should consult their healthcare provider if they experienced delivery complications or have specific health concerns. Every move counts—postpartum women should begin gradually and progress at their own pace.

Defining the Postpartum Period

The postpartum period refers to the time following childbirth when a woman's body is gradually returning to its pre-pregnancy state. This period begins immediately after delivery, known as the acute postpartum phase, and continues through several stages. The early postpartum phase typically lasts from 6 to 8 weeks, followed by the mid postpartum phase, which extends from 6 to 8 weeks up to 6 months. Late postpartum can last up to 12 months, or even longer if breastfeeding. During this time, it is important to modify physical activity, especially in the early stages, to support recovery and accommodate the body's changes.

Guidelines:

It is recommended that:

- For most postpartum women, physical activity levels similar to those recommended for the general population- at least 2 hours and 30 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic activity per week, can gradually be resumed after childbirth.
- Prior to clearance from a healthcare provider, light intensity activity is encouraged in the early weeks, progressing gradually to moderate and vigorous intensity as recovery of musculoskeletal and pelvic structures allows.
- Postpartum women should include muscle-strengthening exercises that focus on major muscle groups throughout the week.

- For postpartum women, pelvic floor muscles exercises (Kegel exercises) should begin in the early postpartum period.

It is recommended that:

- All postpartum women should limit prolonged periods of sitting or lying down during waking hours and avoid extended periods of inactivity. Replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity) provides health benefits.

Good Practice Statements

Postpartum women may transition back to most forms of physical activity after delivery although modifications may be necessary. Light intensity activity such as walking, stretching and postural exercises can be resumed as soon as possible. For other types of activities, a gradual progression is recommended, especially after a caesarean delivery or complications following a vaginal delivery. Where these are present, postpartum women should consult a healthcare provider for clearance.

Postpartum women should consider incorporating aerobic activities such as brisk walking, cycling, dancing, or low-impact aerobics after vaginal wounds are healed. Activities like pram walking offer a great way to incorporate physical activity with baby and support mental well-being and bonding between mother and baby.

In early postpartum, women should avoid activities that place excessive strain on healing tissues, particularly after a caesarean or vaginal delivery complications such as perineal repair. In these cases, a healthcare provider should provide medical clearance to resume activities such as heavy lifting, high impact activities, intense abdominal exercises and strenuous stretching.

In the early postpartum period, it's recommended to wait until pelvic structures have stabilised and postpartum bleeding has completely stopped before engaging in water-based exercises such as swimming or aqua aerobics. Once recovered, water exercises can be a great low-impact option to rebuild strength and support recovery.

Engaging in regular physical activity while breastfeeding is safe and beneficial for both mother and baby. Moderate-intensity exercise does not negatively affect milk production, nutrient composition, or infant growth. In fact, staying active can improve maternal health, enhance mood, and boost energy levels during the postpartum period.

Hydration is important, particularly while breastfeeding. Breastfeeding women should ensure they stay hydrated during and after exercise and wear a supportive bra to ensure comfort. Physical activity should be timed around breastfeeding sessions, such as expressing before sessions, as exercising with full breasts can be uncomfortable.

The 'talk test' is a simple and effective method to gauge the intensity of physical activity during the postpartum period. During moderate-intensity exercise, postpartum women should be able to carry on a conversation but not sing. Intensity should be adjusted as postpartum phases progress and under the supervision of a healthcare provider or exercise professional if there are concerns.

Warning signs to cease activity include persistent dizziness, chest pain, excessive shortness of breath upon physical exertion, heavy vaginal bleeding, or pain that doesn't subside with rest. Postpartum women should consult a healthcare provider immediately if any of these occur.

Specific Populations

Inactive: Postpartum women who were inactive before or during pregnancy should begin with light-intensity activities, such as short walks. Gradually aim to build up to 2 hours and 30 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic activity per week, starting with short sessions (10-15 minutes) and increasing duration as fitness improves.

Active: Women who were habitually physically active prior to, and during pregnancy, may be able to resume activity fairly quickly. Aim to transition back to 2 hours and 30 minutes to 5 hours of moderate-intensity aerobic activity per week, incorporating vigorous activity when comfortable. Progress gradually and consult with a healthcare provider for individual recommendations.

Highly active/athletes: Women who were highly active or athletes before pregnancy may resume vigorous-intensity physical activity as long as it feels comfortable and is done with the guidance of a healthcare provider. Return gradually and allow time for your body to adjust postpartum, particularly after delivery.

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Messages for postpartum women

1. You should aim to stay physically active during your postpartum recovery. Physical activity helps you recover, improves your mood, and promotes better sleep. (what)

- Staying active can reduce your risk of postpartum depression, help you lose pregnancy weight gradually, and improve your overall well-being. (why)
- Start with light-intensity activities, like walking, and gradually build up to moderate-intensity exercise. Consult your healthcare provider if you had complications during delivery. (how)

2. Muscle-strengthening exercises are important for rebuilding strength postpartum. (what)

- These exercises help improve posture, supports recovery, and aids in everyday tasks like lifting and carrying your baby. (why)
- Aim to do muscle-strengthening exercises a few times a week. Start gently and increase intensity as you feel stronger. If unsure, consult a healthcare provider or exercise professional. (how)

3. Pelvic floor exercises (Kegel exercises) should be incorporated into your daily routine. (what)

- These exercises can begin early and are important to help strengthen the muscles supporting your bladder, uterus, and bowel, preventing urinary incontinence and aiding recovery. (why)
- Perform pelvic floor exercises by contracting and relaxing the muscles used to stop urination. Aim to do them daily and consult a healthcare provider or exercise professional if you have any concerns. (how)

4. You should aim to limit the time spent sitting down or lying down during the day as prolonged sedentary behaviour creates health risks. (what)

- You may find that you are sitting or lying down more during early postpartum, particularly if you are breastfeeding and while your body needs rest and recovery. Try to take breaks from sitting for prolonged periods and incorporate some light intensity activities. Replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity including light intensity is important for your health. (Why/How)
- As your recovery progresses, gradually reduce sedentary behaviour by incorporating light physical activity into your daily routine, such as gentle walking or pelvic floor exercises. You may still need ample rest but aim to break up long periods of sitting with simple movements that support your recovery and mental well-being. (Why/How)
- As you continue to heal, focus on increasing physical activity while minimising extended periods of inactivity. Incorporating moderate-intensity activities, such as pram walking or aerobic exercises,

can help counteract the effects of sedentary behaviour, contributing to overall health and improved postpartum recovery. (Why/How)

Messages for Health and Social Care Professionals and Practitioners

Physical activity during pregnancy provides a wide range of benefits, including reducing the risk of chronic conditions like gestational diabetes, hypertension, and excessive gestational weight gain. It also supports mental health, helps manage stress, and improves sleep quality during pregnancy and after birth.

In the early postpartum phase, staying active helps restore physical strength, improves mood, reduces the risk of postpartum depression, and aids in regaining functional movement for daily tasks, including caring for the baby.

Pregnancy and postpartum is an ideal time to encourage behaviour change and the adoption of a healthy lifestyle due to increased motivation regarding maternal and fetal health and frequent access to medical supervision. Leverage these opportunities to promote physical activity.

Many women reduce their level of physical activity during pregnancy and after childbirth. The pregnancy and postpartum period are an opportune time for you to recommend or reinforce physical activity and provide tailored advice to help women resume physical activity safely. Pregnant women are more likely to engage in physical activity if their healthcare provider recommends it.

Consider integrating motivational counselling techniques, such as brief interventions, into routine care for women with uncomplicated pregnancies. This can help increase their engagement in physical activity.

Carefully evaluate women with medical or obstetric complications before making physical activity recommendations. Monitor these patients closely to ensure the safety of any physical activity programmes they undertake.

Pregnant women should be informed by their healthcare provider of the danger signs alerting them as to when to stop; or to limit physical activity and consult a qualified health-care provider immediately should they occur.

It remains important to identify any contraindications before women begin or return to physical activity during the postpartum period. Exercise routines may be resumed gradually as soon as medically safe, depending on the mode of delivery and individual factors. Light physical activity, pelvic floor muscle

exercises, walking, postural, functional exercises, and stretching can usually be resumed immediately, provided there are no complications.

Some women may need to restrict their activity during pregnancy due to contraindications. It is still important for these women to avoid excessive inactivity.

While staying active at work is encouraged, pregnant women should avoid prolonged heavy lifting or strenuous physical tasks. Pregnant women may need accommodations in the workplace and employers and healthcare providers should work together to ensure a safe and supportive work environment.

Myths about physical activity being harmful to pregnant and postpartum women should be dispelled. Health professionals should emphasise that physical activity is not only safe but beneficial for most pregnant women and can be adapted to suit their specific health needs, abilities, or concerns.

Particularly for women with disabilities or health concerns, it's essential to personalise physical activity advice and adapt exercises to accommodate their needs while still promoting movement.

Messages for Physical Activity/Sport Professionals and Practitioners

The relationship between physical activity and health is clear for pregnant and postpartum women. Staying physically active during and after pregnancy provides significant health benefits for both mother and baby. Even small increases in physical activity contribute to improved health and quality of life for pregnant and postpartum women, aiding in recovery and reducing health risks.

Regular physical activity during pregnancy and postpartum helps manage weight, reduces the risk of gestational diabetes, pre-eclampsia, and postpartum depression, and promotes better sleep and mood. For postpartum women, exercise can also accelerate recovery and reduce stress. Encourage women to stay active as they transition into motherhood.

Strengthening activities are essential during and after pregnancy. During pregnancy, they help develop muscle strength to support the body's changes, improve posture, and reduce back pain. Postpartum, they aid in recovery, rebuild muscle, and help manage daily tasks like lifting and carrying the baby.

Approximately 60% of pregnant women experience low back pain. Strengthening abdominal and back muscles can help minimise this risk and provide additional support throughout pregnancy.

Recent evidence demonstrates that there is no minimum amount of physical activity required to achieve some health benefits.

Even aiming to do at least 10 minutes of activity at a time can be effective as a behavioural goal for pregnant and postpartum women starting from low levels of activity.

Pregnancy results in significant anatomical and physiological changes, such as weight gain, a shift in the centre of gravity, and increased forces across joints. These factors should be considered when prescribing exercise to pregnant women.

The principles of exercise prescription for pregnant women do not differ from the general population. Most pregnant women can exercise safely, provided they receive appropriate guidance and modifications as necessary. Ensure that exercises are adapted to the specific physiological and anatomical changes of pregnancy.

Develop and adjust exercise programmes for pregnant women that lead to an eventual goal of 2 hours and 30 minutes of moderate activity spread throughout the week. Adjust these programmes based on medical conditions and individual needs.

Endurance training during pregnancy can increase aerobic capacity in normal-weight and overweight women. This can have long-term health benefits for both the mother and baby.

The Rate of Perceived Exertion (RPE) scale is a useful way to monitor exercise intensity for pregnant women. Moderate intensity should be around 13-14 ("somewhat hard") on the Borg scale or use the 'talk test'. Exercising at a higher intensity may also be beneficial, especially for women accustomed to such exercise before pregnancy.

Women's participation in physical activity tends to diminish after childbirth. Physical activity professionals should encourage women to stay active postpartum, using gradual progression and tailored advice based on their recovery status.

Light physical activity, along with pelvic floor muscle exercises, should be encouraged as soon as possible postpartum. These exercises can help reduce the risk of urinary incontinence and promote recovery. Other activities can gradually resume as soon as it is medically safe. Tailor exercise recommendations to each woman's mode of delivery, medical or surgical complications, and overall recovery. Some women may resume physical activity within days of delivery, while others may need more time to recover.

Abdominal strengthening exercises have been shown to reduce the incidence of diastasis recti abdominis and decrease the inter-rectus distance in women who gave birth vaginally or via caesarean. Incorporate safe and appropriate core exercises for postpartum recovery.

Opportunities for women to be active with their babies can help empower women to embrace physical activity not only for their health, but also as a means of nurturing their relationship with their babies.

Breastfeeding women should be provided information on the benefits of staying active while breastfeeding. Support women to adjust their exercise routines and encourage hydration and proper nutrition to support both their activity levels and breastfeeding needs.

Being inactive during pregnancy and postpartum can be harmful to health. Regular movement helps prevent complications such as excessive weight gain, gestational diabetes, and postpartum depression. Encourage women to stay active, even with light-intensity activities.

DRAFT

Appendix 2: Link to Published National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland for Pregnant and Postpartum Women with the Final Guidelines and Messages

<https://www.hse.ie/eng/about/who/healthwellbeing/our-priority-programmes/health/every-move-counts/hse-physical-activity-guidelines-for-pregnant-and-postpartum-women.pdf>

Appendix 3: Agenda for Stakeholder Consultation Meeting

09:30 – 10.00	Registration and Refreshments
10.00 – 10.10	Welcome <i>Prof. Mary Horgan, Chief Medical Officer</i>
10.10 – 10.20	Opening Address <i>Dr. Cliona Murphy, National Clinical Director National Women and Infants Health Programme</i>
10.20 – 10.40	Development of the Draft Guidelines and Messages <i>Aisling McGrath, SETU</i>
10.40 – 10.55	Purpose, Structure and Content of the Guidelines <i>Prof. Michael Harrison, SETU</i>
10.55 – 11.25	Discussion 1: Pregnancy <i>Stakeholders</i>
11.25 – 11.55	Discussion 2: Postpartum <i>Stakeholders</i>
11.55 – 12.25	Discussion 3: Messages for Professionals <i>Stakeholders</i>
12.25 – 12.30	Close <i>Sarah O'Brien, HSE</i>
12.30 – 1.30	Lunch

Appendix 4: Outline of Discussion Rounds for Stakeholder Consultation Meeting

Discussion Round 1: Pregnancy Guidelines and Messaging (30 minutes)

Introduction by moderator (2 minutes)

Key objectives

- **Enhancing Clarity and Specificity (6 minutes)**
 - How can we provide more actionable guidance within the public health scope? (e.g., exercise examples, trimester-specific considerations).
 - Can the guidelines include more concrete examples of safe aerobic, strength, and pelvic floor exercises (including light intensity exercises)?
 - Can we include practical examples of stretching, postural, and balance exercises suitable for pregnant women?
 - Can we add more practical suggestions in relation to breaking up sedentary time?
 - Can we add clarity to understanding of different exercises intensities?
 - How much more specific can we be about what to avoid (e.g., certain activities, modifications for PGP/SPD) without exceeding the scope?
 - What level of specificity is realistic within the scope of public health guidelines?
 - What level of clarity can we add in relation to specific signposting to HCPs?

Summarise recommendations (2 minutes)

- **Tone and Accessibility (6 minutes)**
 - How can we ensure the language supports pregnant women without being overly prescriptive or inducing pressure?
 - How can we balance PA promotion with messages about rest, recovery and self-compassion and individual limitations?
 - How can the tone be adjusted to better support and reassure women, especially those with high-risk pregnancies or fatigue-related barriers?
 - How can we ensure language is inclusive, clear, and supportive?

Summarise recommendations (2 minutes)

- **Inclusivity (6 minutes)**
 - Can the messaging/guidelines be adjusted to be more inclusive of all women (e.g., inactive women, those with disabilities, highly active women, and women with complex pregnancies)?
 - Are there adjustments to make the guidelines feel more relevant to underrepresented groups/ Consider SES barriers?

Summarise recommendations (2 minutes)

Discussion 2: Postpartum Guidelines and Messaging (30 mins)

Moderator introduces session (2 minutes)

Key Objectives

1. Clarity and Practicality (6 minutes)

- Can we include general timelines or thresholds for resuming activity after C-section or vaginal delivery while keeping the guidance accessible to all?
- Can we offer advice on when to resume common activities such as running?
- Should the guidelines offer practical tips for light daily movement and examples of suitable exercises (e.g., core rehab, pelvic floor, gentle strength)?
- What level of clarity can we add in relation to specific signposting to HCPs?
 - What suggestions are there for clearer identification of the healthcare providers involved in postpartum exercise?

Summarise recommendations (2 minutes)

2. Tone and Balance (6 minutes)

- How can we better balance the importance of movement with messages about recovery, rest, and adapting to fatigue or childcare demands?
- How can we adjust language to avoid prescriptive tones, particularly for minimising inactivity?
- How can we Address concerns about sedentary messaging to ensure it's achievable and non-judgmental for new mothers?

Summarise recommendations (2 minutes)

3. Inclusivity (6 minutes)

- Should there be more explicit mention of the diversity of postpartum experiences?
- Can we acknowledge mental and emotional wellbeing more explicitly?
- Do the guidelines/messages adequately account for barriers such as time, fatigue, or breastfeeding?
 - Is there room to incorporate more activities that involve baby?

Summarise recommendations (2 minutes)

Note: There was lower consensus on the practicality of the guidelines

Discussion 3: Messages for Professionals (30 mins)

Key Objectives

1. Supportive Guidance (6 minutes)

- Are the messages clear and actionable for professionals working with general populations?
- How can we enhance messaging to help professionals feel supported in delivering these guidelines?
- What could make the messages more user friendly for professionals?

Summarise recommendations (2 minutes)

2. Consistency Across Professional Groups: (6 minutes)

- Does the messaging align across health, social care, and sport/exercise professionals?
- How can we refine the language to improve accessibility?

Summarise recommendations (2 minutes)

3. Scope of Recommendations (6 minutes)

- How much should the guidelines address specific signposting to healthcare providers (e.g. physiotherapists)?
- Should these messages be clarified further to address areas of uncertainty, or are they adequately nuanced for public health guidelines?
- Are there any areas where the messages should be simplified or made more specific?

Summarise recommendations (2 minutes)

Pregnant and Postpartum Women

We want to hear from you!

South East Technological University on behalf of the HSE are developing the first national guidelines for Ireland to support physical activity during pregnancy and postpartum - and we need *your voice!*

If you're pregnant or have given birth in the last 12 months your views matter - help us ensure these guidelines reflect the needs of women from all backgrounds.

← Take the Survey here!

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Do you work with pregnant and postpartum women?

Your expertise is needed!

South East Technological University on behalf of the HSE are developing the first national guidelines for Ireland to support physical activity during pregnancy and postpartum - and we need *your voice!*

If you're a physical activity, sports, health or social care professional who works with pregnant and postpartum women, we need your insights on shaping the national physical activity guidelines

← Take the Survey here!

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The National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland for Pregnant and Postpartum Women - Final Research Report

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